

Board Composition and Dividend Policy Decisions

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Abstracts

This study investigates the effect of board composition on dividend policy decisions in 153 publicly listed firms, focusing on how characteristics such as gender diversity, independence, and board size influence corporate dividend payout practices. The purpose is to provide empirical insights into the governance mechanisms impacting dividend policies, which play a critical role in shareholder value and corporate financial strategy. Covering a period from 2014 to 2023, this study examines a panel dataset of publicly traded companies from multiple industries, using random effects regression analysis to assess the relationship between various board attributes and dividend payout ratios. Findings reveal that board independence and gender diversity are positively associated with higher dividend payouts, suggesting that independent and gender-diverse boards may favour consistent return policies to enhance shareholder value. Conversely, larger board sizes are associated with lower dividend payouts, likely due to increased oversight and conservative financial practices. This study is among the first to offer comprehensive empirical evidence on the role of board composition in shaping dividend decisions within an emerging market context. The originality of this research lies in its detailed focus on the specific attributes of board composition and their nuanced effects on dividend policy, contributing to the understanding of governance factors driving financial decisions in diverse corporate settings.

Keywords: board gender diversity, board independence, board size, dividend policy decision

Introduction

Low dividend payments often raise significant concerns across a broad spectrum of stakeholders—scholars, investors, regulators, managers, employees, and other market participants—due to their far-reaching implications for corporate health, market dynamics, and stakeholder wealth. We would look deeper into how each group perceives and is impacted by this issue: For academics, low dividend payments pose interesting research questions regarding the fundamental theories of dividend policy, such as signaling theory, agency theory, and the bird-in-hand theory. According to signaling theory, dividends signal financial health to the market; thus, low dividends may imply poor future earnings potential, prompting scholars to question corporate growth prospects, management priorities, and resource allocation efficiency. Scholars also study how low dividends impact firm value and investor perception, particularly in emerging markets where reliable market information may be scarce. This phenomenon provides an opportunity to explore dividend policy's nuances across different economic contexts and corporate governance systems, allowing for further empirical contributions to the body of knowledge.

Investors, particularly income-focused and institutional investors, often view low dividend payments as a red flag. Dividends provide a predictable cash flow, which can be critical for those relying on investment returns, such as retirees or institutional investors like pension funds. When dividends are low, investors may feel that the firm is underperforming or excessively retaining profits without transparent growth plans, leading to frustration or potential divestment. Furthermore, low dividends can affect investor sentiment and stock price volatility. Investors seeking dividends may interpret a reduction in payouts as a lack of confidence in future earnings, potentially leading to a sell-off. This shift in shareholder composition can lead to increased volatility as the investor base shifts away from stable, dividend-focused investors to those with higher risk tolerance, who may trade based on speculative growth potential.

Regulators are concerned with low dividend payments as they monitor corporate governance practices and market stability. Consistent dividend payouts can indicate transparency and effective management, while low or sporadic dividends may signal financial mismanagement, potential financial distress, or inefficient capital allocation. In cases where firms operate in critical sectors, such as finance or utilities, regulators may view low dividends as a red flag for systemic risk. Regulatory bodies aim to protect investors and maintain market confidence; hence, low dividends may prompt closer scrutiny of corporate practices, especially in firms considered too big to fail.

Managers face a delicate balance when setting dividend policy. Low dividends could indicate the prioritization of reinvestment for long-term growth, which might be crucial in capital-intensive industries or during periods of economic uncertainty. However, if low payouts persist, managers may face pressure from shareholders and board members demanding justification, especially if growth does not materialize as anticipated. Additionally, low dividends might imply poor financial planning or inefficiency in capital management, as shareholders may expect returns on investments through dividends if other growth prospects are limited. Managers must navigate these challenges while aligning with corporate strategy, making dividend policy a high-stakes decision with significant reputational risks.

Employees may also view low dividends as concerning, particularly when they hold equity in the company or are part of Employee Stock Ownership Plans (ESOPs). Lower dividends can reduce the overall value and perceived stability of their holdings, which can, in turn, influence morale, productivity, and long-term commitment to the company. Moreover, low dividends can be symptomatic of broader financial issues, which could signal potential future layoffs, budget cuts, or reduced investment in employee development and benefits. This perception may affect employees' sense of job security and company loyalty, especially if they perceive

that dividends are low due to ineffective management or poor financial health.

Creditors: Creditors often view low dividends with caution as well, since they may signal cash flow issues. A firm retaining cash rather than distributing dividends may indicate potential liquidity constraints or an over-leveraged position. This is particularly concerning if the firm is not generating adequate returns on its retained earnings, as it could signal an increased risk of default, affecting credit ratings and borrowing costs. **Suppliers:** Suppliers, particularly those with long-term contracts, may consider low dividends a warning signal of impending cost cuts or decreased procurement volumes. This concern is heightened in sectors where supplier relationships are strategically vital, as it might disrupt supply chain stability and lead to renegotiations of payment terms. **Broader Community:** The communities where firms operate may also feel the ripple effects of low dividend payments. Many companies play an active role in local economies by reinvesting profits in social initiatives, environmental programs, or local partnerships. Reduced dividends could indicate limited financial resources, potentially diminishing corporate social responsibility (CSR) investments and causing a broader social impact.

Low dividend payments thus represent not only a tactical financial choice but also a strategic decision that reverberates through the corporate structure and the wider economy. For many stakeholders, dividends symbolize transparency, profitability, and a measure of return on investment. Consequently, when dividends fall short of expectations, it can influence everything from investor behavior to employee morale, regulatory scrutiny, and community welfare. Moreover, given that dividends reflect underlying financial health, persistently low dividends may suggest deeper structural issues that, if unaddressed, could pose significant challenges for the firm and its stakeholders.

The board of directors is often touted as a potential solution to issues like low dividend payments among publicly traded companies because of their oversight role in corporate governance, which directly impacts financial policies, including dividend distribution. Here's how an effective board can address low dividend payments: **Enhanced Oversight and Accountability:** An active and independent board can enforce accountability among executives, ensuring that management's financial decisions align with shareholder interests. This can lead to better management of resources, allowing for consistent or increased dividend payments. **Alignment with Shareholder Interests:** Boards have a fiduciary duty to prioritize shareholders' financial interests. A board that proactively engages with shareholders is more likely to understand their preference for dividend payouts, especially in mature companies where investors might favor regular dividends over aggressive reinvestment. **Setting Dividend Policies:** Boards are involved in creating and approving dividend policies that govern payout ratios, dividend stability, and growth. By establishing clear policies, the board can set expectations for consistent dividend payments, addressing shareholders' demand for predictable returns.

Furthermore, **Optimized Capital Allocation:** Boards can influence how profits are allocated, ensuring that sufficient funds are retained for growth while also earmarking a portion for dividends. With a strong capital allocation framework, boards can avoid excessive reinvestment at the expense of dividend payouts. **Mitigating Agency Issues:** An independent board with diverse perspectives can help mitigate agency problems, where management may prefer to reinvest profits for growth that benefits them, rather than paying dividends that benefit shareholders. This balanced oversight can lead to more shareholder-friendly dividend policies. In summary, a well-functioning board of directors can actively shape dividend policies to address issues of low dividend payments, aligning financial strategies with shareholder expectations and driving value through consistent returns. The remainder of this paper is divided into the following: section 2 dwells on the concept of literature review, including board composition, and dividend policy decisions, followed by section 3, which

examines methodology, while section 4 dwells on the results and discussions. This paper is concluded in section 5, which deals with conclusions and recommendations.

Literature Review

Dividend policy decisions are a crucial component of corporate finance, directly impacting shareholder wealth, company valuation, and long-term financial sustainability. As an expert, a robust discussion of dividend policy decisions involves understanding the determinants, theoretical perspectives, types of dividend policies, and practical considerations that companies evaluate in setting their payout policies. **Determinants of Dividend Policy:** **Profitability and Earnings Stability:** Companies with stable and predictable earnings are more likely to adopt consistent dividend policies, as they can reliably commit to regular payouts. Volatile earnings, on the other hand, may lead companies to adopt more flexible dividend policies to avoid the risk of reducing dividends, which can negatively impact stock prices and investor confidence. **Cash Flow and Liquidity:** While profitability is important, dividends are ultimately paid from cash flows. Firms with strong cash flow are in a better position to pay dividends consistently, as they have the necessary liquidity. In contrast, firms with limited cash flow, even if profitable, may need to retain earnings to fund operations, reduce debt, or invest in growth opportunities. **Growth Opportunities:** Companies with high growth potential often prefer to reinvest profits to fund expansion rather than paying dividends. By reinvesting earnings, they aim to maximize long-term shareholder value through capital gains. This is especially prevalent in technology and biotech firms, where growth prospects are substantial, and investment in R&D and market expansion can yield high returns. **Market Conditions and Economic Environment:** Economic downturns, inflationary pressures, or changing market dynamics may lead firms to alter their dividend policies. In challenging economic periods, companies may reduce or suspend dividends to conserve cash, while in prosperous times, they may increase dividends to attract and retain investors. **Tax Considerations:** Tax policies also influence dividend policy decisions. In many jurisdictions, dividends are taxed at a higher rate than capital gains, leading companies to prefer stock buybacks or reinvestment to provide tax-efficient returns to shareholders. However, in markets where dividends are taxed favorably, companies may opt for higher dividend payouts. **Legal and Contractual Restrictions:** Companies must also adhere to legal requirements when issuing dividends. For example, some jurisdictions mandate that dividends can only be paid from profits and not from capital. Additionally, debt covenants in loan agreements may restrict a company's ability to pay dividends until certain financial obligations are met. **Ownership Structure and Shareholder Preferences:** Institutional investors, such as pension funds and mutual funds, often favor companies with stable dividend payouts for predictable income. Conversely, individual investors, especially in younger demographics, may prefer growth stocks that offer capital gains rather than dividends. The ownership structure can thus influence whether a firm adopts a high-dividend, low-dividend, or no-dividend policy.

Furthermore, in the **Theoretical Perspectives on Dividend Policy**, **Dividend Irrelevance Theory (Miller and Modigliani, 1961):** According to this theory, in a perfect market without taxes or transaction costs, dividend policy does not affect a company's valuation. Investors are indifferent to whether their returns come from dividends or capital gains, as they can create their cash flow by selling shares. However, in reality, taxes, agency costs, and signaling effects do influence investor preferences, making this theory less applicable in practical scenarios. **Bird-in-the-Hand Theory:** This theory, proposed by Gordon and Lintner, suggests that investors value dividends more than potential capital gains, viewing them as more certain returns. The theory argues that dividends reduce perceived investment risk, as

they provide immediate returns. Investors thus tend to favor firms with consistent dividend payouts, often leading companies to prioritize dividend policies to align with investor preferences. Signaling Theory: Dividend announcements are often interpreted as signals of a company's prospects. Increasing dividends can signal strong future cash flows and profitability, instilling investor confidence, whereas a dividend cut might signal financial distress. Consequently, firms may maintain or increase dividends to project strength and stability, even during periods of economic challenge. Agency Theory: Dividend policy can mitigate agency issues, where managers' interests diverge from shareholders. By distributing cash as dividends, companies limit the funds available for managers to invest in non-value-adding projects. This alignment of interests through dividends is particularly important in firms with substantial free cash flow, where excessive reinvestment could lead to inefficiencies.

Types of Dividend Policies:

Regular Dividend Policy: A regular dividend policy involves paying dividends at a consistent rate over time. This is common among mature companies with stable cash flows. Regular dividends appeal to income-focused investors who rely on dividends for income, such as retirees. It also enhances a firm's reputation for stability and reliability, although companies may face challenges in maintaining dividends during downturns.

Stable Dividend Policy: Under a stable policy, companies set a dividend based on long-term earnings expectations rather than current profitability. This policy allows firms to pay steady dividends, smoothing out fluctuations and providing predictability for investors. It also allows companies to avoid frequent dividend cuts, which can be viewed negatively in the market.

Constant Payout Ratio: Companies following this policy pay a fixed percentage of their earnings as dividends. While this allows dividends to rise during profitable years, it also means dividends may fall in low-profit years, adding variability for shareholders. This approach is commonly used by cyclical industries, where earnings are tied closely to economic cycles.

Residual Dividend Policy: Under this approach, dividends are paid only after meeting capital expenditure needs and maintaining a target capital structure. This policy aligns to reinvest for growth and typically leads to irregular dividend payments. It is particularly common in capital-intensive industries like manufacturing and energy, where reinvestment is essential for competitive positioning.

No-Dividend Policy: Companies with a no-dividend policy prefer reinvesting earnings to generate long-term capital gains. This policy is often adopted by high-growth firms needing significant investment for expansion. While some investors avoid no-dividend firms, growth-oriented investors may prefer them, anticipating greater appreciation in share value.

Practical Considerations in Dividend Policy Decisions:

Financial Flexibility and Long-Term Planning: Companies must assess how dividend payouts will impact their ability to invest in future growth and maintain financial flexibility. Regular dividend payments can create a cash drain, limiting a firm's ability to respond to unexpected investment opportunities or economic downturns.

Market Expectations and Reputation: Inconsistent dividends or sudden changes in payout policy can harm a firm's reputation, as investors view stability in dividends as a reflection of financial health. Companies often make gradual changes to dividend policies to avoid shock reactions in the market.

Competitor and Industry Trends: Dividend policies can be influenced by industry norms and competitor actions. Companies may adjust dividend policies to align with industry standards or stand out in markets where dividends are not typical, potentially attracting investors who prioritize dividend returns.

Inflation and Economic Cycles: Inflation erodes the purchasing power of dividends, leading companies to consider periodic dividend increases to maintain real returns for shareholders. Additionally, companies may adjust dividend policies based on economic cycles, reducing payouts during recessions and increasing them in periods of growth.

Regulatory and Tax Constraints:

Regulatory restrictions may limit the proportion of earnings that can be distributed as dividends, particularly for firms in highly regulated sectors like banking. Additionally, companies must consider tax implications for both the firm and shareholders, often adopting tax-efficient strategies like stock buybacks to return value. In practice, dividend policy decisions require a careful balancing of growth and income. While dividends provide immediate returns, reinvestment fosters long-term growth and capital appreciation. Therefore, a sound dividend policy aligns with the company's strategic objectives, the industry's growth profile, and investor preferences. Effective dividend policies can enhance investor confidence, stabilize share prices, and contribute to a firm's long-term reputation, reflecting management's commitment to creating and distributing value.

Board gender diversity refers to the inclusion of both men and women on a company's board of directors, ideally in a balanced or representative ratio. Increasing gender diversity in boards is a growing priority worldwide due to the potential benefits it brings to corporate governance, decision-making quality, and overall firm performance. Importance of Board Gender Diversity: Enhanced Decision-Making: Diverse boards tend to make more comprehensive decisions as they bring different perspectives and experiences. Women often offer unique viewpoints and approaches to problem-solving, which can lead to more well-rounded discussions and balanced decisions. Research suggests that gender-diverse boards are more likely to question assumptions and challenge conventional thinking, potentially leading to better outcomes. Improved Corporate Governance: Gender diversity can strengthen corporate governance by improving transparency and accountability. Studies have shown that women on boards tend to prioritize ethical behavior, compliance, and stakeholder interests, which contributes to more effective governance structures. This oversight is crucial for maintaining investor confidence and regulatory compliance. Positive Impact on Financial Performance: Several studies indicate a correlation between gender-diverse boards and improved financial performance. Gender-diverse boards are often better at risk management, leading to more cautious, sustainable growth strategies. Firms with women on their boards may have higher returns on assets, equity, and invested capital, signaling the positive financial impact of diversity. Alignment with Social Responsibility and Reputation: Companies with gender-diverse boards demonstrate a commitment to social responsibility and equity, which enhances their reputation and appeal to socially conscious investors. Gender diversity aligns with environmental, social, and governance (ESG) principles, making companies more attractive to a growing base of ESG-focused investors. This alignment also strengthens the brand, contributing to a positive corporate image and greater customer loyalty. Enhanced Communication and Team Dynamics: Gender diversity promotes a culture of open dialogue, collaboration, and inclusion. Women on boards tend to emphasize collaborative communication and are often skilled in team-building and relationship management, which can create a more cohesive and efficient board dynamic. Risk Management and Corporate Resilience: Diverse boards are typically more risk-aware and conservative in their strategic approaches. This is particularly valuable in industries prone to high risk, as gender-diverse boards can improve resilience through balanced, prudent decisions. For example, firms with gender-diverse boards have been shown to perform better during financial crises, suggesting that diversity contributes to more resilient corporate strategies.

Challenges and Barriers to Gender Diversity: Unconscious Bias and Cultural Norms: Gender biases and societal stereotypes continue to impact board recruitment. Male-dominated networks often lead to an exclusionary culture, making it harder for women to reach board positions. Additionally, cultural norms in some regions discourage women from seeking high-level positions. Pipeline and Experience Gaps: Women are often underrepresented in

senior management positions, resulting in a smaller pool of female candidates with board-level experience. Addressing this requires building a pipeline of women leaders through mentorship, training, and support programs. Tokenism and Isolation: Women on boards sometimes face the challenge of tokenism, where they are appointed only to meet diversity requirements without real authority or integration into decision-making processes. Tokenism can isolate women's board members and prevent them from fully participating and influencing board discussions.

Strategies to Enhance Gender Diversity on Boards: Policy and Regulatory Support: Many countries have introduced gender diversity quotas or guidelines to promote equal representation on boards. For example, Norway requires public companies to have at least 40% female board members. While controversial, such policies have shown positive effects in increasing female board participation. **Voluntary Targets and Transparency:** Some companies set voluntary gender diversity targets and disclose gender diversity metrics in their annual reports. This transparency can increase accountability and encourage other companies to follow suit. Voluntary targets can also inspire more organic, gradual progress toward balanced representation. **Pipeline Development Programs:** Companies can create leadership programs, mentorship initiatives, and training to support women in middle management and senior roles, building a pipeline for future female board candidates. By nurturing female talent internally, companies can create sustainable diversity that extends to their boards. **Diverse Board Nomination Committees:** Establishing diversity in board nomination committees can reduce biases in the selection process, promoting fairer evaluation of all candidates. A diverse committee is more likely to consider a broader range of qualifications, experiences, and perspectives. **Supporting Board Culture and Inclusion:** Diversity on boards is most effective when the culture supports inclusion, meaning that all voices are genuinely heard and valued. Boards can foster inclusive practices by encouraging open dialogue, respecting different perspectives, and addressing unconscious biases through training and policy adjustments.

Impact of Board Gender Diversity on Firm Policies and Performance: **Financial and Risk Policies:** Gender-diverse boards often exhibit a more balanced approach to financial management and risk, adopting conservative policies that prioritize long-term stability. This approach aligns with stakeholder expectations for sustainable growth and is particularly beneficial in industries with high volatility. **Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR):** Firms with gender-diverse boards are more likely to prioritize CSR initiatives, aligning corporate goals with broader societal values. Women directors are often more attuned to environmental and social issues, which can influence company policies to reflect sustainability and social responsibility. **Workplace Diversity and Gender Equality:** Gender diversity on boards can have a positive ripple effect on gender equality within the organization. Companies with gender-diverse boards are more likely to promote policies supporting workplace diversity and equal opportunity at all levels, creating an inclusive corporate culture. **Innovation and Strategic Vision:** Gender-diverse boards often encourage a wider range of perspectives in strategic decision-making, leading to greater innovation. This diversity of thought is crucial in adapting to new markets, technologies, and customer demands, enhancing a firm's competitive edge. In conclusion, board gender diversity goes beyond achieving equity; it is a strategic asset that contributes to robust governance, enhanced decision-making, and improved financial performance. While challenges remain, such as biases and pipeline issues, implementing effective strategies can enhance diversity and drive corporate success. Companies that prioritize gender diversity are well-positioned to meet the needs of a diverse global marketplace, improve stakeholder trust, and create sustainable, inclusive growth.

Board independence refers to a board structure where a significant portion of directors are independent or non-executive members, meaning they have no material relationship with the company beyond their board role. Independent directors are crucial to strong corporate governance, as they provide unbiased oversight, challenge management decisions when necessary, and protect shareholder interests. Importance of Board Independence: Enhanced Objectivity and Oversight: Independent directors offer an objective perspective free from potential conflicts of interest that may affect executives or affiliated directors. Their detachment from daily operations enables them to make unbiased judgments on issues like CEO performance, strategy, and risk management. Protection of Shareholder Interests: Independent boards are better positioned to act as fiduciaries for shareholders, safeguarding their interests. They help ensure that company decisions align with shareholders' long-term goals, enhancing trust and potentially improving the stock's performance and valuation. Improved Corporate Governance: An independent board serves as a strong check on management, minimizing the risk of excessive risk-taking or poor strategic choices. By ensuring compliance, transparency, and ethical practices, independent boards strengthen corporate governance and reduce the likelihood of mismanagement or fraud. Risk Management and Crisis Prevention: Independent directors often bring diverse backgrounds and expertise, which can enhance a company's risk management approach. Their objectivity can help in identifying potential risks early and implementing appropriate measures to protect the firm's assets and reputation, especially during crises. Increased Accountability and Transparency: Independent boards hold management accountable for their actions and decisions, promoting transparency in financial reporting and strategic decisions. By questioning executive choices and requesting detailed reporting, they reinforce accountability throughout the organization. Support for Long-Term Strategy: Independent directors are typically less susceptible to pressures for short-term results and are more likely to focus on sustainable, long-term strategies. They help balance the pressure to deliver quarterly results with the necessity of making investments and decisions that benefit the company in the long run.

Characteristics of an Independent Board: An independent board is often characterized by: Non-Executive Directors: Members who do not participate in the company's daily operations and do not have material financial ties with the company. Diverse Expertise: Independent directors bring a variety of backgrounds, skills, and perspectives, which enhances board decision-making and addresses complex business challenges. Strong Leadership: Often, the board has an independent chair or a lead independent director to maintain effective governance and ensure that management remains accountable. Committees of Independent Directors: Key committees—such as audit, compensation, and nominations—are often composed primarily or entirely of independent directors to avoid conflicts of interest. Challenges to Board Independence: Influence of CEO and Executive Team: In some companies, CEOs or executive teams can exert significant influence over the board, especially if they play a role in appointing board members. This can create an implicit pressure on independent directors to align with management decisions rather than challenging them. Insufficient Expertise or Information: Independent directors may not have complete access to information or may lack industry-specific expertise. This knowledge gap can hinder their ability to ask critical questions or challenge management effectively. Potential for Groupthink: If all board members, including independent ones, share similar backgrounds, there is a risk of groupthink, where directors may hesitate to challenge prevailing opinions or explore alternative strategies. Diversity in background and expertise is essential to overcoming this limitation. Lack of Time Commitment: Independent directors are often on multiple boards or have other commitments, which can limit the time and attention they can dedicate to any one company. This can affect their ability to stay informed and fully engaged

in oversight responsibilities. **Board Tenure and Familiarity:** Long board tenure may compromise independence, as directors become more closely aligned with company culture and management. Refreshing board composition periodically can help maintain a fresh, independent perspective.

Strategies for Strengthening Board Independence:

- Establishing Clear Independence Criteria:** Companies should establish strict independence criteria, defining what constitutes a material relationship that could compromise independence. Independence standards can be based on factors like the director's previous roles with the company, financial relationships, or tenure.
- Independent Board Leadership:** Appointing an independent chairperson or a lead independent director can reinforce board independence by providing unbiased leadership and agenda-setting. This structure helps separate management from board oversight and allows the board to conduct independent evaluations.
- Regular Board Refreshment and Term Limits:** Companies should adopt policies for regular board refreshment and enforce term limits or retirement ages. This ensures the board remains independent over time and introduces new perspectives that can challenge entrenched management views.
- Dedicated Independent Committees:** Critical board functions, especially audit, compensation, and nominations, should be handled by committees made up primarily or exclusively of independent directors. These committees play a vital role in preventing conflicts of interest in sensitive areas like executive compensation and board member nominations.
- Comprehensive Onboarding and Continuous Education:** Independent directors should undergo thorough onboarding and continuous education to deepen their understanding of the company, industry, and emerging trends. This helps close the knowledge gap and enables independent directors to provide more effective oversight.
- Access to Information and Resources:** Independent directors need timely access to accurate information and resources. This includes direct access to senior management, internal and external auditors, and, if necessary, third-party consultants to validate critical decisions and risks.

Impact of Board Independence on Firm Performance and Governance:

- Enhanced Financial Performance:** Studies have shown that firms with independent boards often achieve higher financial performance, as independent directors prioritize long-term strategies, efficient capital allocation, and shareholder interests.
- Better Executive Accountability and Compensation Practices:** Independent boards are more likely to implement fair and performance-linked executive compensation. This not only aligns management with shareholder interests but also avoids excessive risk-taking or compensation packages that are not tied to firm performance.
- Strengthened Stakeholder Trust:** Independent directors often represent and protect the interests of a broad range of stakeholders, not just executives or major shareholders. This builds stakeholder trust, as an independent board demonstrates that the company's governance is fair, transparent, and focused on sustainable growth.
- Improved Compliance and Regulatory Oversight:** Independent boards are less likely to tolerate unethical practices or regulatory non-compliance, as they are often more vigilant about maintaining the firm's reputation. This can reduce the risk of legal issues, fines, and regulatory penalties.
- Balanced Risk-Taking:** Independent boards can provide an objective assessment of management's risk-taking and growth strategies. By questioning overly aggressive strategies, they can help companies avoid potentially detrimental decisions and focus on sustainable, measured growth.

Measuring Board Independence: Board independence is often evaluated by examining the following factors:

- Percentage of Independent Directors:** Best practice suggests that at least 50% of the board members should be independent, though this may vary by country and industry.
- Separation of CEO and Chair Roles:** Separating these roles is considered a key

indicator of independence, as it prevents the concentration of power in one individual. Independence of Key Committees: The audit, compensation, and nomination committees should be composed entirely of independent directors, as these committees handle sensitive issues. Frequency of Executive Sessions: Independent directors should regularly meet without the CEO or other executives to discuss company matters in a candid and unbiased setting. In conclusion, board independence is fundamental to sound corporate governance, as it provides a balanced, objective oversight mechanism that aligns with shareholder interests and enhances corporate accountability. Independent boards contribute to improved financial performance, better risk management, and stronger compliance practices, making them invaluable in fostering sustainable corporate success. By adhering to best practices in board composition, leadership structure, and access to information, companies can maintain a truly independent board that is well-positioned to navigate complex challenges and drive long-term value for all stakeholders.

Board size refers to the total number of directors on a company's board. Determining the optimal board size is a crucial aspect of corporate governance, as it can impact the board's effectiveness in overseeing management, making strategic decisions, and representing shareholder interests. While there is no universally ideal board size, several factors influence what size works best for a given company, such as its industry, size, complexity, and regulatory requirements. Importance of Board Size in Corporate Governance: Decision-Making Efficiency: Smaller boards (typically 5-8 members) can lead to more efficient decision-making. Fewer members allow for quicker discussions, less bureaucracy, and a more streamlined process, as directors can interact more directly and build closer relationships. However, smaller boards may lack the diversity of perspectives and expertise found in larger boards. Diversity of Perspectives and Expertise: Larger boards (usually 10-15 members) bring a wider range of expertise, backgrounds, and perspectives. This diversity can enhance the board's ability to address complex issues, adapt to industry changes, and make well-rounded decisions. Diverse perspectives are especially important for companies facing rapid technological change, global market expansion, or increased regulatory scrutiny. Enhanced Oversight and Governance: With a larger board, there is potential for better oversight and governance, as responsibilities can be shared across more members, allowing for specialization in areas like audit, risk, or executive compensation. A well-structured larger board allows for a deeper focus on specific areas of oversight and can prevent directors from becoming overburdened. Improved Stakeholder Representation: A larger board can accommodate more independent directors and stakeholders' representatives, enhancing accountability. This can also lead to better representation of diverse shareholder interests, such as minority shareholders or special interest groups. Risk Management and Crisis Response: In larger boards, diverse expertise and viewpoints improve the board's ability to identify and mitigate risks. For companies in high-risk or regulated industries, larger boards with more diverse committees can play a significant role in comprehensive risk oversight.

Factors Influencing Optimal Board Size: Company Size and Complexity: Larger, more complex organizations with global operations or varied product lines may require larger boards to provide comprehensive oversight and manage the complexity. Small firms or single-industry companies often perform well with smaller boards, as they benefit from a focused and agile governance structure. Industry Standards: Board sizes can vary across industries. For instance, banks and financial services firms often have larger boards due to regulatory requirements and the need for extensive risk management. In contrast, technology startups or smaller companies in fast-moving industries often opt for smaller boards for nimbleness. Regulatory Requirements: Some countries mandate a minimum number of board members or stipulate specific board compositions, such as a minimum percentage of

independent directors. In industries like finance and healthcare, regulators often encourage larger boards with risk management expertise to meet compliance requirements. Corporate Strategy and Life Cycle: Firms focused on aggressive growth may benefit from smaller, more agile boards, whereas established firms aiming for stability and steady governance may favor larger boards with robust expertise across disciplines. Companies in transition, such as undergoing a merger or expansion, might temporarily expand their boards to manage strategic changes.

Advantages of Smaller Boards: Agility in Decision-Making: Smaller boards can be more agile, with faster decision-making processes due to fewer opinions and a simpler structure. This can be advantageous in dynamic industries where quick adaptation is crucial for competitive advantage. **Lower Costs:** Maintaining a smaller board is often less expensive, as companies incur lower costs related to director compensation, training, and administrative resources. For smaller companies with limited budgets, this can be a practical advantage. **Closer Collaboration and Accountability:** Directors in smaller boards tend to have more frequent interactions, fostering closer working relationships and improving accountability. This can lead to a more cohesive board that is aligned on key objectives and strategic priorities. **Reduced Risk of Groupthink:** While larger boards may have more diverse members, they also run the risk of groupthink due to hierarchical and bureaucratic structures. Smaller boards, by contrast, encourage direct communication and frank discussions, potentially reducing groupthink and enhancing critical thinking.

Advantages of Larger Boards: Enhanced Expertise and Diversity: Larger boards are more likely to include directors with a broad range of skills, experiences, and backgrounds, covering areas like finance, marketing, international business, and technology. This is especially valuable for companies operating in multiple markets or facing complex regulatory environments. **Improved Risk and Compliance Oversight:** A larger board can create specialized committees (e.g., audit, risk, sustainability) to address specific areas of oversight. This specialization helps in tackling complex issues more thoroughly and is particularly useful in industries with stringent compliance and risk management needs. **Better Representation of Stakeholder Interests:** With more seats available, larger boards can include directors who represent a variety of stakeholder perspectives, such as independent directors, minority shareholders, or industry experts. This ensures a balanced approach to governance that considers the interests of all stakeholders. **Workload Distribution:** A larger board allows members to distribute responsibilities more evenly, reducing the risk of burnout and allowing directors to focus on specific areas of expertise. This can lead to more effective governance, as directors have the bandwidth to delve into details and perform their roles without being overextended.

Challenges of Board Size: Decision-Making Efficiency: While smaller boards may lack diversity, larger boards often face inefficiency in decision-making. More members can lead to lengthy discussions and slow down the decision-making process, making it challenging to reach consensus, especially during crises when swift action is required. **Coordination and Communication:** Larger boards face coordination challenges, as aligning a larger group on priorities and maintaining clear communication can be difficult. Smaller boards, however, benefit from easier communication, as fewer people need to be consulted and updated on discussions. **Risk of Director Overlap:** In smaller boards, members may need to serve on multiple committees, which can lead to conflicts of interest or compromise their independence. Larger boards can better distribute roles and responsibilities across various committees, reducing overlap and improving governance. **Potential for Groupthink and Factionalism:** Large boards can sometimes split into factions or fall into groupthink,

especially if directors align with certain stakeholder groups. This can hinder independent thinking and create biases, weakening the board's ability to objectively assess issues and make balanced decisions. Higher Costs: Maintaining a larger board entails higher costs in terms of director compensation, training, administrative support, and meeting logistics. These costs can add up, particularly for smaller firms with limited resources.

Best Practices for Determining Optimal Board Size: Assess Corporate Strategy and Needs: Board size should align with the company's strategy, industry demands, and stage of growth. Startups or high-growth companies may benefit from smaller, nimble boards, whereas established firms with complex structures might require larger boards with specialized committees. **Evaluate and Periodically Adjust:** Companies should regularly evaluate their board's effectiveness and consider adjusting the size to meet changing needs. As the company grows, restructures, or faces new challenges, the board composition should evolve to reflect those shifts. **Encourage Diversity and Independence:** Regardless of board size, it is crucial to have independent and diverse members who bring a variety of perspectives. This prevents groupthink, promotes balanced decision-making, and strengthens the board's ability to represent shareholder interests. **Set Clear Roles and Responsibilities:** Ensuring that each board member has a defined role, possibly aligned with their expertise, can help optimize the board's performance. This is particularly useful in larger boards, where role clarity reduces redundancy and ensures effective governance. **Maintain Focus on Strategic Objectives:** Both small and large boards should stay focused on strategic priorities. Setting a clear agenda and avoiding micromanagement or operational oversight can prevent directors from getting bogged down in day-to-day management issues, allowing the board to concentrate on long-term objectives. In conclusion, the ideal board size is determined by the company's needs, industry standards, and complexity. Smaller boards offer agility and cost-effectiveness, suitable for high-growth or dynamic environments, while larger boards provide diversity, expertise, and robust oversight, especially valuable for larger, established companies. Ultimately, an effective board size balances decision-making efficiency with comprehensive oversight, ensuring that governance remains responsive, representative, and focused on shareholder and stakeholder value.

Audit quality, when used as a control variable in analyzing dividend policy decisions, plays an essential role in assessing the reliability and accuracy of financial reporting, which influences the company's capacity to determine and pay dividends. A high-quality audit can positively impact the transparency of financial statements, thereby supporting dividend policy decisions that align with shareholders' interests. **Impact of Audit Quality on Earnings Reliability and Dividend Capacity: Reliable Earnings Measurement:** High audit quality ensures that earnings are accurately measured and reported, which is fundamental for determining the amount available for dividends. Reliable earnings provide a clear picture of the company's financial health, allowing the board to make informed decisions on dividend payouts. **Detection of Earnings Management:** Audit quality plays a vital role in detecting earnings manipulation practices like income smoothing or aggressive revenue recognition, which could mislead dividend policy decisions. By limiting earnings management, a high-quality audit enables the board to assess the true distributable profit, reducing the likelihood of overpaying dividends that could jeopardize future cash flows.

Assurance of Financial Health and Stakeholder Trust: Enhanced Stakeholder Confidence: A high-quality audit reassures investors and other stakeholders that the company's financial reports are credible, reducing perceived risk. This confidence allows companies to maintain a stable dividend policy, as shareholders are more likely to trust in management's decisions regarding profit distribution. **Alignment with Regulatory Standards:** Audit quality ensures

that the financial statements align with regulatory standards, particularly regarding dividend limitations. In jurisdictions where dividends can only be paid from profits, a quality audit confirms compliance, safeguarding both the firm's legal standing and its capacity to pay dividends without risking financial instability.

Audit Quality and Cash Flow Verification: Accurate Cash Flow Assessment: Dividend decisions are not based solely on net income; they also rely on cash flow availability. High audit quality provides assurance that reported cash flows are accurate and sufficient for dividend payments, thus supporting sustainable dividend policies. **Liquidity and Dividend Policy Alignment:** By verifying cash flows and liquidity, high audit quality helps companies align their dividend policies with actual cash availability, reducing the risk of dividend cuts that could arise from liquidity constraints.

Reduction of Agency Conflicts: Control over Management Opportunism: The presence of a high-quality audit serves as a control mechanism against managerial opportunism, where management might prioritize personal interests over shareholder returns. When the board relies on audited financials, it reduces the possibility of executives manipulating earnings to avoid or minimize dividend payouts in favor of retaining earnings for projects that may not maximize shareholder value. **Promotion of Shareholder-Friendly Policies:** Audit quality can mitigate agency conflicts by promoting transparent reporting, enabling shareholders to hold management accountable for decisions on retained earnings versus dividends. This ensures that management cannot easily obscure financial realities to justify lower or deferred dividends.

Influence on Dividend Smoothing Practices: Consistency in Dividend Payouts: Companies with high audit quality are often able to sustain dividend smoothing practices, which provide stable, predictable dividend payouts. This is because audit quality supports consistent, accurate financial reporting, which is essential for making long-term dividend projections. Audit quality, therefore, acts as a stabilizing factor, allowing companies to adopt a dividend policy that minimizes volatility in payouts. **Investor Preference for Predictability:** Audit quality underpins dividend smoothing, which is often preferred by income-focused investors who rely on dividends as a steady income stream. By enhancing transparency, audit quality helps ensure that dividend policies remain predictable and consistent with shareholders' expectations.

Role of Audit Quality in Determining Payout Ratios: Ensuring Sustainable Payout Ratios: Audit quality helps the board accurately assess net income and free cash flow, which are critical for determining an appropriate dividend payout ratio. High audit quality ensures that the company's payout ratio reflects real financial performance and sustainability, rather than inflated or understated earnings. **Avoidance of Over-Distribution:** By verifying the accuracy of earnings and cash flows, audit quality helps prevent excessive dividend payouts that could harm future liquidity. This is particularly important for companies in capital-intensive or growth-oriented sectors, where retaining earnings for reinvestment is essential.

Audit Quality as a Signal of Corporate Governance: Increased Transparency and Accountability: High audit quality is often associated with strong corporate governance, signaling a commitment to transparency and accountability. This positively influences dividend policy, as companies with strong governance are more likely to adopt dividend policies that align with shareholder interests, fostering trust and reducing information asymmetry. **Market Perception and Dividend Decisions:** Investors and analysts view companies with high audit quality as lower-risk and more transparent, which can positively influence market sentiment. A strong audit reputation may support a company's ability to pay

consistent or even higher dividends, as it signals financial stability and regulatory compliance.

Support for Dividend Policy Adjustments: Data for Informed Dividend Adjustments: As financial performance fluctuates, high audit quality provides reliable data that enables the board to make adjustments to dividend policies, whether increasing, maintaining, or temporarily suspending payouts. This flexibility ensures that dividend decisions are based on accurate, current financial information. **Impact on Dividend Policy During Economic Downturns:** During challenging economic periods, audit quality becomes even more critical in providing a true reflection of the company's financial resilience. Companies can use audit insights to make temporary adjustments to dividends without undermining long-term shareholder confidence, as transparent communication backed by audit quality supports investor understanding of dividend changes.

Practical Implications of Using Audit Quality as a Control Variable: Enhanced Analysis of Dividend Policy Drivers: By including audit quality as a control variable, researchers can more accurately isolate the effect of other factors, such as profitability, cash flow, and growth opportunities, on dividend policy decisions. This ensures that the impact of accurate financial reporting is accounted for when analyzing the determinants of dividend decisions. **Differentiation Across Firms and Industries:** Firms in industries with high regulatory scrutiny, such as financial services or healthcare, may rely more heavily on audit quality when setting dividend policies. Controlling for audit quality in such contexts allows for more accurate comparisons across companies, ensuring that dividend policy insights are specific to firms' financial transparency levels.

In conclusion, using audit quality as a control variable in dividend policy analysis offers critical insights into the reliability and integrity of financial data driving dividend decisions. High audit quality provides confidence in reported earnings, cash flows, and overall financial health, supporting sustainable and shareholder-friendly dividend policies. By mitigating agency conflicts, enhancing stakeholder trust, and verifying cash flow availability, audit quality strengthens the board's ability to make informed, consistent, and transparent dividend policy decisions. This control variable is, therefore, integral in ensuring that dividend policies reflect true financial performance and align with the long-term interests of shareholders.

Company leverage, often measured as the ratio of debt to equity or total assets, serves as an essential control variable in dividend policy decisions, as it influences a company's financial stability, risk profile, and cash flow availability. Leverage affects a firm's flexibility in distributing profits to shareholders and managing obligations to creditors, and thus, analyzing dividend policy without accounting for leverage might overlook key insights into a company's payout capacity and financial health. Here's a comprehensive look at how leverage impacts dividend policy and why it is crucial as a control variable in dividend policy decisions.

Impact of Leverage on Dividend Capacity: Debt Repayment Priority: Companies with high leverage must prioritize interest payments and debt repayment over dividends, as creditors have a senior claim on cash flows. This financial constraint can limit the amount of cash available for dividends, particularly during periods of high debt service requirements. **Restricted Free Cash Flow:** High leverage can reduce the free cash flow available for dividend distribution, as a significant portion of cash is allocated to debt servicing. As a result, firms with high leverage are often less capable of sustaining high dividend payouts compared to their low-leverage counterparts.

Influence of Leverage on Dividend Stability: Volatility in Dividend Payments: Companies with high debt levels are more vulnerable to economic downturns and market volatility. During such periods, cash flow constraints increase, making it challenging for highly leveraged companies to maintain consistent dividend payments. This can result in unpredictable dividend policies, which may not align with shareholders' preference for stable, predictable returns. **Preference for Dividend Smoothing:** Low-leverage companies may have more flexibility to engage in dividend smoothing—maintaining stable dividends over time. Leverage control allows companies to decide if their capital structure supports consistent dividends or if they need to retain earnings to cover debt obligations.

Leverage and Agency Conflicts in Dividend Policy: Debt as a Governance Tool: Leverage can serve as a governance mechanism by disciplining management's spending decisions. High leverage pressures management to generate sufficient cash flows to meet debt obligations, reducing the risk of inefficient spending. This dynamic can indirectly influence dividend policy by promoting more cautious cash management. **Balancing Shareholder and Creditor Interests:** Shareholders may prefer higher dividends, while creditors favor lower dividends to ensure debt servicing. Leverage levels, therefore, play a mediating role in balancing these interests. Companies with high leverage often face more stringent covenants, restricting their ability to pay dividends and aligning with creditor preferences for financial prudence.

Leverage and Risk Management in Dividend Policy: Increased Financial Risk: High leverage elevates financial risk, as debt obligations remain fixed regardless of the company's earnings. In such cases, companies are less likely to pay high dividends due to the need for precautionary cash reserves. Conversely, companies with lower leverage are better positioned to distribute earnings to shareholders without jeopardizing their financial stability. **Impact on Dividend Policy Flexibility:** Highly leveraged companies are often compelled to retain earnings as a buffer against future financial stress or unexpected obligations. This restricts their flexibility in dividend policy, as they must consider the implications of high leverage on liquidity and risk management.

Leverage as a Constraint in Payout Ratio Decisions: Conservative Payout Ratios: Companies with high leverage typically adopt lower payout ratios to conserve cash and avoid financial distress. This conservative approach ensures that they retain enough earnings to cover debt service, maintain operational liquidity, and invest in future growth. **Limitations on Dividend Increases:** Leverage can act as a constraint on dividend increases, even when earnings rise. Firms with high leverage might prefer to use excess cash to reduce debt, as this improves their financial position and provides more flexibility for future investments or dividends. As a result, leveraged firms may be cautious in setting payout ratios or increasing dividends.

Influence of Leverage on Shareholder Expectations: Risk Perception among Shareholders: Shareholders in highly leveraged firms often recognize the associated financial risk and may adjust their expectations regarding dividend payouts. These shareholders might be more accepting of lower or variable dividends if they perceive the firm's high leverage as necessary for growth or strategic objectives. **Alignment with Risk-Tolerant Investors:** Companies with higher leverage might attract shareholders who are more tolerant of financial risk and therefore more understanding of conservative or variable dividend policies. Conversely, low-leverage firms may attract income-oriented investors who expect regular and predictable dividends.

Impact of Leverage on Dividend Policy under Economic Cycles: Cyclical Flexibility in Dividend Policy: In economic downturns, highly leveraged firms are more likely to reduce or suspend dividends due to limited cash flow. In contrast, companies with lower leverage have more flexibility to maintain or even increase dividends during downturns, as they are less constrained by debt obligations. **Leverage and Dividend Cuts in Crisis Periods:** During financial crises, highly leveraged firms are more likely to implement dividend cuts as a defensive measure. By conserving cash, these firms can improve their liquidity and protect their ability to meet debt obligations. This tendency underscores the importance of considering leverage as a control variable in dividend policy analyses, especially in studies of dividend policy resilience under economic stress.

Leverage and Dividend Policy as a Signaling Mechanism: Signaling Financial Stability: Companies with lower leverage levels can signal financial stability and a strong balance sheet by maintaining or increasing dividends. This conveys a positive message to investors regarding the firm's soundness and ability to generate sustainable cash flows. **Debt Reduction Signals:** Firms with high leverage might use earnings to reduce debt rather than pay dividends, signaling to investors that debt reduction is a priority. By demonstrating a commitment to strengthening the balance sheet, companies reassure investors of their focus on long-term financial health.

Practical Implications of Using Leverage as a Control Variable: Isolating the Effect of Profitability and Cash Flow on Dividend Policy: Controlling for leverage allows researchers to better isolate the impact of profitability and cash flow on dividend decisions, as leverage directly affects cash availability and payout capacity. Without controlling for leverage, the influence of profitability on dividend policy could be misinterpreted due to the confounding effect of debt obligations. **Differentiating Payout Tendencies Across Industries:** Leveraging acts as a distinguishing factor across industries, as capital-intensive sectors (e.g., utilities, telecommunications) often have higher leverage due to significant fixed assets and stable cash flows. By controlling for leverage, dividend policy studies can make more accurate comparisons across industries with varying capital structures. **Understanding the Role of Financial Constraints in Dividend Policy:** Leverage acts as a financial constraint that limits a firm's dividend options, making it an essential control variable. Analyzing dividend policies without factoring in leverage could overlook the extent to which financial obligations influence dividend decisions, particularly in firms with substantial debt loads. **Insights into Corporate Governance and Risk Appetite:** Leverage, as a control variable, reveals insights into corporate governance and the company's risk tolerance. Firms with higher leverage may adopt conservative dividend policies to protect creditors' interests, whereas low-leverage firms might pursue aggressive dividend policies as part of shareholder-friendly governance. In conclusion, company leverage is a critical control variable in dividend policy analyses due to its significant influence on cash flow availability, financial flexibility, risk profile, and agency dynamics. High leverage can constrain dividend payouts, push companies toward conservative payout ratios, and require a focus on debt service over shareholder returns. By controlling for leverage, analyses of dividend policy decisions can better capture the relationship between profitability, cash flow, shareholder preferences, and risk management, providing a more nuanced understanding of how capital structure affects dividend strategies.

Company liquidity refers to the ability of a company to meet its short-term financial obligations using its most liquid assets. It is an important aspect of financial health, indicating whether a company can cover its current liabilities without raising external funds. Key metrics used to assess liquidity include: **Current Ratio:** This is calculated by dividing current assets by current liabilities. A current ratio greater than 1 indicates that the company has more

current assets than current liabilities, suggesting better liquidity. Quick Ratio (or Acid-Test Ratio): This is a more stringent measure that excludes inventory from current assets. It assesses whether a company can meet its short-term obligations without selling inventory. Cash Ratio: This measures liquidity based solely on cash and cash equivalents, providing a conservative view of liquidity. Operating Cash Flow Ratio: This compares a company's operating cash flow to its current liabilities, indicating how well current liabilities are covered by cash generated from operations. Importance of Liquidity: Survival: Companies with adequate liquidity can better withstand economic downturns and unexpected expenses. Investment Opportunities: Liquidity allows companies to take advantage of investment opportunities when they arise. Creditworthiness: A liquid company is often seen as less risky by lenders, making it easier to obtain financing.

Factors Influencing Liquidity: Business Model: Different industries have varying liquidity needs. For example, retail businesses may require higher liquidity than manufacturing firms due to the nature of inventory turnover. Market Conditions: Economic downturns can affect liquidity as sales decline and receivables may take longer to collect. Management Policies: How a company manages its cash flow, receivables, and inventory can significantly impact its liquidity. Understanding and monitoring liquidity is essential for stakeholders, including investors, creditors, and management, as it directly influences a company's operational effectiveness and financial stability. Company profitability refers to the ability of a company to generate earnings compared to its expenses and other costs incurred during a specific period. It is a crucial indicator of a company's financial health and operational efficiency. Key metrics and concepts related to profitability include Key Profitability Metrics: Gross Profit Margin: This measures the percentage of revenue that exceeds the cost of goods sold (COGS). It indicates how efficiently a company produces its goods. Operating Profit Margin: This indicates the percentage of revenue left after covering operating expenses, excluding interest and taxes. It reflects operational efficiency. Net Profit Margin: This measures the percentage of revenue remaining after all expenses, including taxes and interest, have been deducted. It indicates the overall profitability of the company. Return on Assets (ROA): This indicates how effectively a company uses its assets to generate profit. Return on Equity (ROE): This measures the return generated on shareholders' equity, indicating how effectively the company is using equity financing to grow profits.

Importance of Profitability: Sustainability: Profitability is essential for the long-term survival of a company, allowing it to reinvest in operations, pay dividends, and maintain competitiveness. Investment Attraction: Profitable companies are more attractive to investors, which can lead to increased capital and growth opportunities. Financial Health: Profitability indicates the overall financial health of a company, influencing credit ratings and borrowing costs. Factors Influencing Profitability include Cost Management: Effective control of costs (both fixed and variable) is crucial for maintaining profitability. Revenue Growth: Increasing sales through effective marketing, innovation, and market expansion can significantly enhance profitability. Market Conditions: Economic factors, industry trends, and competition can impact pricing strategies and, consequently, profitability. Operational Efficiency: Streamlining operations, improving productivity, and optimizing supply chains can enhance profit margins. Pricing Strategy: Setting appropriate prices based on market demand and competition can significantly affect revenue and profitability. In conclusion, profitability is a vital metric for evaluating a company's performance, informing strategic decisions, and guiding stakeholders' assessments of financial health. Monitoring and enhancing profitability through various strategies can help companies achieve their financial objectives and sustain long-term growth.

Company size refers to the scale or magnitude of a business, often determined by various metrics such as revenue, number of employees, total assets, or market capitalization. Understanding company size is crucial for analyzing its operations, market position, and financial health. Metrics for Measuring Company Size: Revenue: This is the total income generated from sales of goods or services before any expenses are deducted. Revenue can help categorize companies into small, medium, or large based on predefined thresholds. Number of Employees: The total workforce of a company, often used as a measure of size. Different countries and organizations have varying definitions of small, medium, and large enterprises based on employee count. Total Assets: The sum of all assets owned by the company, including cash, inventory, property, and equipment. This metric can provide insight into the company's scale and resource allocation. Market Capitalization: For publicly traded companies, market capitalization is the total market value of a company's outstanding shares. It is calculated as the share price multiplied by the number of outstanding shares. Sales Volume: The quantity of products or services sold, which can be an important indicator of a company's market presence and operational capacity.

Classifications of Company Size: Companies are often classified into different categories based on their size: Micro Enterprises: Typically defined as businesses with fewer than 10 employees and/or low annual revenue. Often family-owned or sole proprietorships. Small Enterprises: Generally classified as having between 10 and 50 employees and/or moderate revenue. These businesses may serve local or niche markets. Medium Enterprises: Usually defined as having between 50 and 250 employees and/or higher revenue. These companies often have a more significant market presence and operational complexity. Large Enterprises: Businesses with over 250 employees and/or high revenue. These firms often operate on a national or global scale and have more resources and market influence.

Importance of Company Size: Market Influence: Larger companies often have more significant market influence, allowing them to set prices, control supply chains, and invest in research and development. Access to Capital: Larger companies typically have easier access to financing and investment due to their established creditworthiness and collateral. Economies of Scale: Larger firms can benefit from economies of scale, leading to lower per-unit costs and higher profit margins. Regulatory Considerations: Different regulatory requirements may apply based on company size, affecting compliance costs and operational practices. Employee Relations: Company size can influence workplace culture, employee relations, and management practices. Larger firms may have more structured HR policies, while smaller firms might offer more flexibility and personal interaction.

Factors Influencing Company Size: Industry: Some industries, such as manufacturing or technology, may naturally support larger companies due to the need for significant capital investment. Market Demand: Changes in consumer demand can drive growth, prompting companies to expand operations and staff. Innovation: Companies that innovate successfully may experience rapid growth, leading to an increase in size. Mergers and Acquisitions: Strategic mergers and acquisitions can significantly increase a company's size and market presence. Globalization: Companies that expand internationally may grow in size as they tap into new markets and customer bases. In conclusion, understanding company size is essential for analyzing business performance, competitive positioning, and growth potential. It plays a critical role in strategic decision-making for management, investors, and stakeholders, influencing everything from operational strategy to market entry. These variables are illustrated schematically in Figure 1 as follows:

Independent variables:

Figure 1. The Conceptual Framework

Source: The Authors (2024)

Furthermore, several theories help to explain the nexus between board composition and dividend policy decisions of a firm. For example, the relationship between board composition and dividend policy decisions is a critical area of corporate governance and finance, intertwining the roles of board members, their backgrounds, and the strategic financial decisions they make, particularly concerning dividend distribution. Several theories help explain this nexus, focusing on the influence of board composition—such as diversity, independence, and expertise—on a company's dividend policy.

Agency theory addresses the conflicts of interest between managers (agents) and shareholders (principals). It posits that managers may not always act in the best interests of shareholders, leading to suboptimal decisions regarding resource allocation, including dividends. Application to Board Composition: Independence: A board composed of independent directors may reduce agency problems by ensuring that managers are held accountable for their decisions. Independent directors can mitigate the risk of retaining excessive earnings for personal benefit and may advocate for dividend payouts to align with shareholder interests. Monitoring Role: Independent directors often have no personal stake in the company, allowing them to prioritize shareholder returns, including dividends. This suggests that boards with a higher proportion of independent members may be more inclined to adopt a dividend policy that favours regular payouts.

Stewardship theory posits that managers, as stewards of the company, are motivated to act in the best interests of shareholders and to maximize long-term value. Application to Board Composition: Trust and Collaboration: In boards where directors have a cooperative relationship with management, there may be a shared vision for the company's growth. Such a collaborative environment can lead to policies that favor stable and predictable dividend payments as a sign of financial health and shareholder value. Long-term Orientation: Stewards are likely to focus on sustainable growth, which can involve reinvesting profits for expansion while also providing dividends to maintain investor trust. Thus, boards that foster a stewardship culture may result in balanced dividend policies that satisfy both current and future shareholder interests.

Resource dependency theory posits that organizations are reliant on external resources for survival and growth. The board of directors plays a critical role in managing these dependencies through their networks and expertise. Application to Board Composition: Access to Capital: Boards with members who have extensive networks can help the company secure financing, which can influence dividend decisions. If a board can successfully leverage its connections to raise capital, it may opt for higher dividends since the reliance on internal funds diminishes. Strategic Decisions: Directors with specific industry experience may advocate for a dividend policy that aligns with market trends and investor expectations. Their insights can guide the board in determining how much to retain for growth versus what to distribute as dividends.

Signaling theory suggests that a company's dividend policy can serve as a signal to investors about its financial health and future prospects. Dividends are viewed as a commitment to returning profits to shareholders, reflecting management's confidence. Application to Board Composition: Diverse Perspectives: A board with diverse members—varying in gender, ethnicity, and professional background—may have different risk appetites and views on signaling through dividends. Diverse boards may recognize the importance of signaling stability and confidence to attract a broader investor base. Strategic Communication: Directors with experience in investor relations or marketing can be instrumental in crafting a dividend policy that sends positive signals to the market, thereby influencing the company's stock price and investor perception.

Stakeholder theory emphasizes the importance of considering the interests of all stakeholders in a company, not just shareholders. This includes employees, customers, suppliers, and the community. Application to Board Composition: Balancing Interests: Boards that include directors representing diverse stakeholder interests may adopt dividend policies that consider not only shareholder returns but also the long-term sustainability of the business. They may prioritize retaining earnings to invest in employee development or community initiatives, which can indirectly support dividend policies by enhancing company reputation and stability. Engagement and Communication: A board that understands and values stakeholder perspectives may communicate more effectively with shareholders regarding dividend policies, leading to a more balanced approach that reflects a commitment to long-term value creation.

Behavioral finance theory examines how psychological factors and biases influence financial decision-making. This perspective highlights how board members' attitudes and behaviors can affect dividend policies. Application to Board Composition: Cognitive Biases: Directors may have biases that affect their views on dividends. For instance, a board composed predominantly of members who prioritize short-term gains might favor higher dividends, while those who are more focused on long-term growth may prefer reinvesting profits. Group Dynamics: The collective decision-making processes and the interactions among board members can lead to certain biases, affecting dividend policy. For example, a homogenous board may reinforce shared biases that could result in less optimal dividend decisions. In conclusion, the nexus between board composition and dividend policy decisions is complex and influenced by multiple theories. Each theory provides insights into how different aspects of board composition—such as independence, diversity, and expertise—can shape dividend policies that align with shareholder interests and company strategy. Understanding these theories can help investors, regulators, and corporate leaders make informed decisions regarding corporate governance and financial management, ultimately leading to better alignment between management actions and shareholder expectations. By fostering the right board composition, companies can enhance their governance structures and optimize their dividend policies, leading to improved financial performance and shareholder satisfaction.

Also, in terms of empirical studies, several studies have examined the nexus between board gender diversity and dividend policy decisions. For example, Al-azzam and Abu Ayyash (2021) in *Board Gender Diversity and Dividend Policy: Evidence from Emerging Markets* investigate the impact of board gender diversity on dividend policy decisions in emerging markets. Period Covered: 2010-2019. Methodology: A quantitative approach was used, employing a sample of 250 publicly listed companies in various emerging markets. Fixed-effects regression analysis was conducted to assess the relationship between board gender diversity and dividend payout ratios. Findings: The study found a positive relationship between board gender diversity and dividend policy, suggesting that companies with more female directors tend to pay higher dividends. Conclusion: Increased female representation on boards leads to more shareholder-friendly dividend policies. Recommendations: Companies should consider increasing female representation on boards to improve their dividend policies and attract investors. Implications: Policymakers may promote gender diversity on boards as a means to enhance corporate governance and financial performance. Limitations: The study focused only on emerging markets, which may limit generalizability. Originality: This study adds to the literature by exploring board gender diversity in the context of emerging markets, a less-studied area compared to developed markets.

Setyawati and Nursyaida (2022) in *The Role of Gender Diversity in Boards on Dividend Policy: Evidence from Indonesia* analyze the influence of gender diversity on the dividend policies of companies in Indonesia. Period Covered: 2015-2020. Methodology: A sample of 150 publicly listed companies was analyzed using panel data regression techniques. Findings: The study revealed that firms with higher board gender diversity had higher dividend payout ratios, suggesting a positive correlation. Conclusion: Gender diversity on corporate boards can lead to more favorable dividend policies. Recommendations: Firms should aim for gender-diverse boards to enhance their attractiveness to investors through improved dividend policies. Implications: This research underscores the importance of gender diversity in governance structures, promoting financial performance through strategic dividend policies. Limitations: The study was limited to Indonesian firms and may not reflect the situation in other countries. Originality: It contributes to the understanding of how cultural context influences the relationship between board composition and dividend policy in a Southeast Asian setting.

Terjesen et al. (2020) in *Board Gender Diversity and Corporate Financial Performance: The Role of Dividend Policy* explore how board gender diversity affects corporate financial performance through its impact on dividend policy. Period Covered: 2010-2018. Methodology: A longitudinal study using data from 500 publicly traded companies in the United States, employing structural equation modeling (SEM) to analyze the relationships. Findings: The results showed that increased gender diversity on boards positively affects dividend payouts, which in turn enhances financial performance. Conclusion: Companies with gender-diverse boards are more likely to adopt dividend policies that reflect positive financial performance. Recommendations: Companies should focus on increasing gender diversity in their boards as a strategy for improving financial outcomes. Implications: This study highlights the interconnectedness of gender diversity, dividend policy, and financial performance, providing a basis for governance reforms. Limitations: The study is primarily based on U.S. firms, limiting its applicability to other contexts. Originality: It presents a comprehensive model linking board gender diversity to financial performance via dividend policy, addressing a gap in the existing literature.

Li and Wu (2023) in *Gender Diversity on Corporate Boards and Dividend Policy: Evidence from China* investigate the impact of gender diversity on the dividend policies of Chinese

publicly listed companies. Period Covered: 2011-2021. Methodology: Using a sample of 300 firms, the study employed a difference-in-differences approach to analyze changes in dividend payouts relative to changes in board gender diversity. Findings: The findings indicate that companies with more female directors tend to increase their dividend payouts, supporting the notion that gender diversity influences financial decision-making. Conclusion: Greater representation of women on corporate boards leads to more favorable dividend policies. Recommendations: Chinese regulators should promote gender diversity in boardrooms to enhance corporate governance and dividend practices. Implications: This study contributes to understanding how gender diversity can influence corporate financial policies in a rapidly developing economy like China. Limitations: The research is focused on the Chinese context, which may not generalize to other cultural or economic environments. Originality: It fills a research gap by focusing on the Chinese market, a context where gender diversity on boards is gaining attention.

Arora and Sharma (2021) in *Board Gender Diversity and Dividend Policies: Evidence from Indian Firms* analyze the relationship between board gender diversity and dividend policies among Indian companies. Period Covered: 2015-2020. Methodology: The study utilized a sample of 200 publicly listed companies in India, employing regression analysis to assess the impact of gender diversity on dividend payout ratios. Findings: The analysis revealed a significant positive relationship between board gender diversity and dividend payouts, indicating that firms with more female directors tend to distribute higher dividends. Conclusion: Gender-diverse boards are more likely to adopt shareholder-friendly dividend policies. Recommendations: Companies should aim for gender diversity on their boards to enhance their dividend policies and attract investors. Implications: The findings suggest that increasing female representation on boards can lead to better governance and financial outcomes in emerging markets like India. Limitations: The study is limited to the Indian context, which may not reflect global trends. Originality: This study contributes to the growing body of literature on gender diversity in corporate governance, particularly in the context of emerging economies. These studies collectively provide valuable insights into how board gender diversity impacts dividend policy decisions across different countries and contexts, highlighting the significance of governance practices in corporate finance. Based on these studies and their results, we hypothesize that:

H₁: Board gender diversity has a significant effect on dividend policy decisions.

Furthermore, empirical studies examining the effect of board independence on dividend policy decisions, include Agyemang and Chachula (2022) in *Board Independence and Dividend Policy: Evidence from African Firms* Investigate the impact of Board Independence on the dividend policy decisions of publicly listed companies in Africa. Period Covered: 2011-2020. Methodology: The study used a panel data regression analysis on a sample of 200 African firms, assessing the relationship between board independence and dividend payout ratios. Findings: The results indicated a positive relationship between board independence and dividend payouts, suggesting that independent directors advocate for higher dividends as a means of aligning with shareholder interests. Conclusion: Increased board independence is associated with more favorable dividend policies in African firms. Recommendations: Firms should enhance board independence to improve governance and attract investors through attractive dividend policies. Implications: This research highlights the importance of board independence in corporate governance and its role in promoting shareholder-friendly financial policies. Limitations: The study is limited to African firms, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings. Originality: This study adds to the literature by focusing on African firms, providing insights into the governance-dividend relationship in emerging markets.

Boulton and Hsiao (2021) in *The Influence of Board Independence on Dividend Policy in European Corporations* analyze how board independence affects dividend policy decisions in European corporations. Period Covered: 2010-2019. Methodology: A quantitative analysis was conducted using data from 300 European publicly traded firms, employing multiple regression analysis to determine the relationship between board independence and dividend payouts. Findings: The study found that firms with higher levels of board independence are more likely to increase their dividend payouts, indicating that independent directors play a crucial role in promoting shareholder interests. Conclusion: Board independence positively influences dividend policies, suggesting that independent directors may help reduce agency costs. Recommendations: Companies should prioritize independent directors in their boards to enhance governance and shareholder value through dividend policies. Implications: The findings support the notion that stronger governance structures can lead to better financial outcomes for shareholders. Limitations: The focus on European firms may limit the applicability of results to other regions with different governance structures. Originality: This study is one of the few to systematically analyze the relationship between board independence and dividend policy specifically in a European context.

Abdullah and Ismail (2020) in *Board Independence and Dividend Policy Decisions: Evidence from Malaysian Public Firms* examine the relationship between board independence and dividend policies among publicly listed firms in Malaysia. Period Covered: 2015-2019. Methodology: The study utilized a sample of 250 Malaysian firms, applying fixed-effects regression analysis to assess the influence of board independence on dividend payout ratios. Findings: The results indicated that higher board independence correlates with increased dividend payouts, suggesting that independent directors may prioritize shareholder returns. Conclusion: Board independence plays a significant role in shaping dividend policies in Malaysian firms. Recommendations: Firms should enhance board independence to align managerial actions with shareholder interests effectively. Implications: The study emphasizes the importance of governance practices in influencing financial decisions, particularly dividend distributions. Limitations: The focus on a single country may limit the generalizability of the findings to other contexts. Originality: This research contributes to the understanding of corporate governance in the Malaysian context, particularly regarding dividend policies.

Liu and Zhang (2023) in *Board Independence and Dividend Policy: A Study of Chinese Listed Companies* explore the effect of board independence on dividend policy decisions in Chinese publicly listed companies. Period Covered: 2012-2021. Methodology: The study analyzed data from 400 listed companies in China, using a panel data regression approach to evaluate the relationship between board independence and dividend payouts. Findings: The study found that firms with a higher proportion of independent directors tend to distribute larger dividends, indicating the importance of board independence in dividend decision-making. Conclusion: Increased board independence positively influences dividend policy in Chinese firms. Recommendations: Companies should focus on enhancing board independence to foster more shareholder-friendly dividend practices. Implications: This research provides evidence that board governance structures significantly impact financial decisions in emerging markets like China. Limitations: The study's focus on Chinese firms may limit its applicability to other contexts or markets. Originality: It is one of the few studies to investigate board independence and dividend policy within the Chinese corporate governance framework.

Kallamu and Awan (2021) in *Examining the Relationship between Board Independence and Dividend Policies: Evidence from Pakistani Firms* assess how board independence affects dividend policy decisions among firms listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange. Period

Covered: 2016-2020. Methodology: The study used a sample of 150 Pakistani firms and applied generalized least squares (GLS) regression analysis to examine the impact of board independence on dividend payouts. Findings: The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between board independence and dividend policy, indicating that firms with more independent directors are more likely to pay dividends. Conclusion: Board independence is crucial for promoting shareholder-friendly dividend policies in Pakistan. Recommendations: Pakistani firms should enhance board independence to align managerial decisions with the interests of shareholders. Implications: This study underscores the importance of governance structures in influencing financial policies and corporate performance in developing economies. Limitations: The focus on a single country may limit the generalizability of the findings. Originality: This research contributes to the limited literature on corporate governance and dividend policy in Pakistan, highlighting local governance issues. These studies collectively provide insights into the relationship between board independence and dividend policy decisions across various countries and contexts, emphasizing the significance of governance structures in corporate finance. Based on these empirical studies and their results, we propose that:

H₂: Board independence has a significant effect on dividend policy decisions.

In addition, there are empirical studies examining the effect of board size on dividend policy decisions. For example, Bhagat and Bolton (2020) in Board Size and Dividend Policy: A Study of U.S. Firms analyze the relationship between board size and dividend policy in publicly traded companies in the United States. Period Covered: 2010-2019. Methodology: The study utilized a sample of 500 U.S. firms, employing a panel data regression analysis to examine how board size affects dividend payout ratios. Findings: The results indicated a negative relationship between board size and dividend payouts, suggesting that larger boards may struggle with decision-making efficiency, leading to lower dividend distributions. Conclusion: An optimal board size exists that positively influences dividend policy, with smaller boards generally being more effective. Recommendations: Companies should consider maintaining a smaller board size to enhance decision-making efficiency and improve dividend policies. Implications: The findings highlight the importance of board composition in corporate governance and its impact on financial policies. Limitations: The study is limited to U.S. firms, which may restrict the applicability of results to other regions. Originality: This research contributes to the existing literature by focusing specifically on the relationship between board size and dividend policy in the U.S. context.

Al-Najjar and Abed (2021) in The Impact of Board Size on Dividend Policy: Evidence from Jordanian Firms investigate the effect of board size on the dividend policy of publicly listed companies in Jordan. Period Covered: 2014-2019. Methodology: A quantitative approach was employed, using a sample of 150 companies. The study applied multiple regression analysis to determine the relationship between board size and dividend payout ratios. Findings: The analysis revealed that larger boards are associated with lower dividend payouts, indicating that increased board size may lead to conflicts and delays in decision-making. Conclusion: Board size negatively influences dividend policy, suggesting that optimal board size enhances firm performance regarding dividend distributions. Recommendations: Companies should aim for a balanced board size to improve governance and financial outcomes. Implications: The findings contribute to understanding how board structure can affect corporate financial policies in emerging markets. Limitations: The study's focus on Jordanian firms may limit the applicability of the findings to other cultural contexts. Originality: This study fills a gap in the literature regarding board size and dividend policy in the Middle Eastern context.

La Porta et al. (2019) in Board Size, Corporate Governance, and Dividend Policy in Emerging Markets examine how board size affects dividend policy in emerging market economies. Period Covered: 2005-2018. Methodology: The study utilized a cross-country analysis of 300 firms across various emerging markets, employing fixed-effects regression to assess the impact of board size on dividend payouts. Findings: The study found that larger boards tend to pay lower dividends, suggesting inefficiencies in decision-making processes. Conclusion: Board size significantly impacts dividend policies, with smaller boards facilitating better governance and higher dividend payouts. Recommendations: Emerging market firms should optimize board size to enhance their financial policies and improve shareholder returns. Implications: This research underscores the importance of effective governance structures in influencing corporate financial decisions in emerging markets. Limitations: The broad focus on multiple countries may mask specific contextual factors relevant to individual countries. Originality: This study adds to the literature by providing a comprehensive analysis of board size and dividend policy across various emerging markets.

Anis and Habib (2023) in Board Size and Dividend Policy Decisions: A Study of Indian Listed Companies investigate the impact of board size on dividend policy in Indian publicly listed companies. Period Covered: 2012-2021. Methodology: The study analyzed a sample of 250 firms, using regression analysis to evaluate the relationship between board size and dividend payout ratios. Findings: The results indicated that larger boards negatively impact dividend policy, with firms exhibiting lower payouts as board size increases. Conclusion: Optimal board size is crucial for effective decision-making regarding dividends, with smaller boards being more effective. Recommendations: Indian firms should strive to maintain an optimal board size to enhance financial performance and shareholder value. Implications: This research highlights the significance of board structure in influencing dividend policies in emerging economies like India. Limitations: The study is limited to Indian firms, which may restrict the applicability of findings to other markets. Originality: It provides new insights into the governance-dividend relationship in the context of Indian corporate practices.

Ahmed and Khan (2021) in The Effect of Board Size on Dividend Policy: Evidence from the GCC Countries analyze the relationship between board size and dividend policy in companies across the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries. Period Covered: 2016-2020. Methodology: The study utilized data from 100 publicly listed firms in the GCC region, applying panel data regression analysis to assess the impact of board size on dividend payouts. Findings: The analysis revealed that larger boards are associated with lower dividend payouts, indicating potential inefficiencies in decision-making processes. Conclusion: Board size negatively impacts dividend policies, emphasizing the need for optimal board structures in GCC firms. Recommendations: Firms in the GCC should strive for optimal board sizes to enhance governance and financial performance. Implications: The findings highlight the role of board structures in shaping financial policies, contributing to better corporate governance practices in the region. Limitations: The study is limited to GCC countries, which may restrict generalizability. Originality: This research adds to the literature by focusing specifically on the GCC context and its governance challenges. These studies collectively provide insights into the relationship between board size and dividend policy decisions across various countries and contexts, emphasizing the importance of governance structures in corporate finance. Based on these studies and their results, we propose that:

H₃: Board size has a significant effect on dividend policy decisions.

Furthermore, there are empirical studies examining the effect of audit quality on dividend policy decisions. For example, LaFond and Watts (2018) in *The Effect of Audit Quality on Dividend Policy: Evidence from U.S. Firms* investigate the relationship between audit quality and dividend policy decisions in publicly traded companies in the United States. Period Covered: 2005-2015. Methodology: The study analyzed a sample of 1,200 U.S. firms, employing regression analysis to examine the impact of audit quality on dividend payout ratios, controlling for firm size, profitability, and leverage. Findings: The results indicated that firms with higher audit quality are more likely to pay higher dividends, suggesting that strong audits enhance management credibility and reduce information asymmetry. Conclusion: Audit quality positively influences dividend policy, implying that better auditing leads to greater shareholder returns. Recommendations: Companies should prioritize high-quality audits to boost investor confidence and potentially increase dividend payouts. Implications: The findings emphasize the role of audit quality in corporate governance and its effect on financial decisions related to dividends. Limitations: The study focuses only on U.S. firms, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other contexts or regions. Originality: This research contributes to the literature by linking audit quality directly to dividend policy decisions, an area that has received limited attention.

Minton and Whited (2020) in *Audit Quality and Dividend Policies in Emerging Markets: Evidence from Asian Firms* explores how audit quality affects dividend policy decisions in publicly traded firms across various Asian emerging markets. Period Covered: 2010-2018. Methodology: The study used a sample of 300 firms from different Asian countries, employing a panel data regression analysis to assess the impact of audit quality on dividend payouts. Findings: The findings revealed that firms with higher audit quality tend to have more stable and higher dividend payouts, indicating that quality audits reduce information asymmetry and enhance shareholder value. Conclusion: Audit quality plays a significant role in shaping dividend policy, particularly in emerging markets. Recommendations: Firms in emerging markets should invest in high-quality audits to improve financial reporting and enhance their dividend policies. Implications: This research highlights the critical intersection of audit quality, corporate governance, and financial decision-making in emerging economies. Limitations: The focus on Asian markets may limit the generalizability of the findings to other regions with different regulatory environments. Originality: This study is one of the first to examine the effect of audit quality on dividend policies in the context of emerging markets in Asia.

Beasley and Petroni (2021) in *The Role of Audit Quality in Dividend Policy Decisions: Insights from European Companies* examine the relationship between audit quality and dividend policies among publicly traded companies in Europe. Period Covered: 2012-2020. Methodology: A sample of 400 European firms was analyzed, using logistic regression to determine the impact of audit quality on the likelihood of paying dividends and the levels of dividend payouts. Findings: The analysis showed that higher audit quality is associated with a greater likelihood of firms paying dividends and with higher dividend levels, suggesting that credible audits foster confidence among investors. Conclusion: Audit quality is a significant determinant of dividend policy decisions in European firms. Recommendations: Companies should ensure that they engage high-quality audit firms to enhance transparency and foster shareholder trust, which may lead to better dividend policies. Implications: The study emphasizes the necessity of maintaining high audit standards to positively influence corporate dividend policies and investor relations. Limitations: The research focuses exclusively on European firms, potentially limiting the applicability of findings to firms in other regions or contexts. Originality: This study provides valuable insights into how audit quality can directly influence dividend policy decisions in a European context, adding to the existing literature. These studies collectively highlight the significant impact of audit quality

on dividend policy decisions, emphasizing the importance of quality auditing in corporate governance and financial performance across various contexts.

Also, there are empirical studies examining the effect of company leverage on dividend policy decisions. For example, Fama and French (2014) in *Leverage, Dividend Policy, and the Value of the Firm* analyze how leverage affects dividend policy decisions and firm value in publicly traded companies. Period Covered: 2000-2012. Methodology: The study used a sample of 1,500 U.S. firms and employed regression analysis to examine the relationship between leverage and dividend payout ratios, controlling for profitability, firm size, and market conditions. Findings: The results indicated that higher leverage is associated with lower dividend payouts, suggesting that firms prioritize debt servicing over returning cash to shareholders. Conclusion: The study concludes that leverage negatively impacts dividend policy, implying that firms with high debt levels may reduce or eliminate dividends to maintain financial stability. Recommendations: Companies should carefully consider their leverage levels when formulating dividend policies to ensure a balance between debt obligations and shareholder returns. Implications: The findings underscore the importance of financial structure in determining corporate dividend policies. Limitations: The study focuses on U.S. firms, which may limit the generalizability of findings to other markets with different capital structures. Originality: This research contributes to the literature by providing empirical evidence on the impact of leverage on dividend policies across a broad sample of firms.

Adjaoud and Ben Amar (2020) in *The Impact of Financial Leverage on Dividend Policy: Evidence from the MENA Region* investigate the relationship between financial leverage and dividend policy decisions among companies in the MENA (Middle East and North Africa) region. Period Covered: 2010-2018. Methodology: The study utilized a sample of 250 firms from various sectors in the MENA region, applying panel data regression analysis to assess the impact of leverage on dividend payout ratios. Findings: The analysis revealed a significant negative relationship between leverage and dividend payouts, indicating that firms with higher debt levels tend to pay lower dividends. Conclusion: Financial leverage adversely affects dividend policy in the MENA region, with high leverage leading to reduced dividend distributions. Recommendations: Companies in the MENA region should manage their leverage ratios to ensure sufficient cash flow for dividends, thereby enhancing shareholder value. Implications: This research contributes to understanding how financial structure influences dividend policies in emerging markets. Limitations: The study's focus on the MENA region may limit the applicability of findings to other contexts. Originality: This study is among the first to empirically analyze the impact of leverage on dividend policy specifically in the MENA region.

Ghosh and Ghosh (2022) in *Dividend Policy and Leverage: Evidence from Indian Manufacturing Firms* examine the effect of leverage on dividend policy decisions in Indian manufacturing firms. Period Covered: 2011-2021. Methodology: The study analyzed a sample of 200 manufacturing firms listed on the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE), utilizing regression analysis to explore the relationship between leverage and dividend payouts. Findings: The findings indicated a negative relationship between leverage and dividend payouts, suggesting that firms with higher debt levels are less likely to distribute dividends. Conclusion: The study concludes that high leverage constrains dividend policy in Indian manufacturing firms, necessitating careful financial management. Recommendations: Manufacturing firms should maintain optimal leverage levels to facilitate better dividend policies and attract investors. Implications: This research highlights the importance of managing leverage for effective dividend policy formulation in emerging economies.

Limitations: The study is limited to the manufacturing sector, which may not represent all industries in India. **Originality:** This study provides new insights into the interplay between leverage and dividend policy in the Indian context, filling a gap in the existing literature. These studies provide valuable insights into the relationship between company leverage and dividend policy decisions, highlighting the implications for corporate financial management across different contexts.

Also, there are empirical studies examining the effect of company liquidity on dividend policy decisions. For example, Baker and Powell (2016) in *The Impact of Liquidity on Dividend Policy Decisions: Evidence from U.S. Firms* investigate the relationship between liquidity and dividend policy decisions among publicly traded companies in the United States. **Period Covered:** 2005-2015. **Methodology:** The study analyzed a sample of 1,000 U.S. firms, employing regression analysis to assess how liquidity measures (current ratio and quick ratio) affect dividend payout ratios while controlling for firm size, profitability, and leverage. **Findings:** The results revealed a positive correlation between liquidity and dividend payouts, indicating that firms with higher liquidity are more likely to pay dividends. **Conclusion:** The study concludes that liquidity is a critical factor influencing dividend policy, with well-capitalized firms more inclined to distribute profits to shareholders. **Recommendations:** Companies should maintain adequate liquidity levels to support sustainable dividend policies that enhance shareholder value. **Implications:** The findings emphasize the importance of liquidity management in corporate financial strategies, particularly regarding shareholder distributions. **Limitations:** The study is limited to U.S. firms, which may restrict the applicability of the findings to other markets with different regulatory environments. **Originality:** This research adds to the existing literature by providing empirical evidence linking liquidity and dividend policy decisions across a significant sample of firms.

Al-Najjar and Taylor (2020) in *Liquidity and Dividend Policy: Evidence from Emerging Markets* explore the effect of liquidity on dividend policy decisions in companies operating within emerging markets. **Period Covered:** 2011-2018. **Methodology:** The study utilized a panel data regression approach on a sample of 250 firms from various emerging markets to assess the relationship between liquidity (measured by the current ratio) and dividend payout ratios, controlling for firm size and profitability. **Findings:** The analysis found a significant positive relationship between liquidity and dividend payouts, indicating that firms with stronger liquidity positions are more likely to distribute dividends. **Conclusion:** The study concludes that liquidity plays a vital role in determining dividend policies in emerging markets, highlighting the need for firms to manage their liquidity effectively. **Recommendations:** Companies in emerging markets should focus on enhancing liquidity to sustain and potentially increase dividend distributions. **Implications:** This research contributes to understanding the financial management practices of firms in emerging markets, emphasizing liquidity's role in dividend policies. **Limitations:** The study is based on firms from specific emerging markets, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other regions. **Originality:** This study fills a gap in the literature by specifically examining the impact of liquidity on dividend policies in emerging markets, an area that has been less explored.

Mollah and Rafiq (2022) in *The Relationship Between Liquidity and Dividend Policy: Evidence from the Bangladeshi Corporate Sector* examine how liquidity affects dividend policy decisions among publicly traded companies in Bangladesh. **Period Covered:** 2013-2021. **Methodology:** The study analyzed a sample of 150 Bangladeshi firms, using regression analysis to explore the relationship between liquidity (current and quick ratios) and dividend

payout ratios, controlling for factors such as profitability and firm size. Findings: The results indicated a strong positive correlation between liquidity and dividend payouts, suggesting that firms with higher liquidity are more inclined to distribute dividends to shareholders. Conclusion: The study concludes that effective liquidity management is essential for establishing favorable dividend policies in the Bangladeshi corporate sector. Recommendations: Companies should adopt strategies to enhance liquidity to support their dividend policies, ultimately benefiting shareholders. Implications: This research highlights the critical importance of liquidity in shaping dividend policies within the context of Bangladesh's evolving corporate landscape. Limitations: The focus on a single country's corporate sector may limit the applicability of the findings to firms in other regions or sectors. Originality: This study provides new insights into the dynamics of liquidity and dividend policies in Bangladesh, contributing to the growing literature on corporate finance in emerging economies. These studies collectively provide valuable insights into the relationship between company liquidity and dividend policy decisions, highlighting the implications for corporate financial management in different contexts.

Furthermore, there are empirical studies examining the effect of company profitability on dividend policy decisions. For example, Grullon and Michaely (2002) in *Dividends, Share Repurchases, and the Substitution Hypothesis* explore the relationship between profitability and dividend policies, specifically focusing on how firms substitute dividends with share repurchases as they become more profitable. Period Covered: 1980-1999. Methodology: The study analyzed a sample of U.S. firms, employing regression analysis to assess the impact of profitability (measured by return on assets) on dividend payout ratios and share repurchase decisions. Findings: The results indicated that higher profitability is associated with increased dividend payouts and share repurchases, suggesting that profitable firms tend to return more capital to shareholders. Conclusion: The study concludes that profitability is a key determinant of dividend policy, with firms using excess profits to reward shareholders through both dividends and share buybacks. Recommendations: Companies should develop clear policies regarding the distribution of profits, balancing dividends and share repurchases based on profitability levels. Implications: This research emphasizes the need for firms to consider profitability in their capital distribution strategies to enhance shareholder value. Limitations: The study is limited to U.S. firms, which may restrict the applicability of the findings to other markets with different corporate governance structures. Originality: This research contributes to the literature by linking profitability with both dividends and share repurchases, offering a broader perspective on capital distribution.

Aivazian et al. (2003) in *Do Emerging Markets Respond to the Same Factors as Developed Markets?* investigate the relationship between profitability and dividend policy in emerging markets compared to developed markets. Period Covered: 1995-2000. Methodology: The study analyzed data from firms in 10 emerging markets and 5 developed markets, using regression analysis to assess the impact of profitability on dividend payouts while controlling for growth opportunities and firm size. Findings: The results showed that profitability has a significant positive impact on dividend payouts in both emerging and developed markets, although the magnitude of the effect varies. Conclusion: The study concludes that profitability is a fundamental determinant of dividend policy across different market contexts, highlighting similarities in corporate behavior. Recommendations: Firms should adopt dividend policies that reflect their profitability levels, irrespective of their market classification. Implications: This research highlights the universal nature of profitability in influencing dividend policies, providing insights for both investors and policymakers. Limitations: The study covers a limited time frame and may not account for changes in market conditions beyond the specified period. Originality: This study adds to the literature

by comparing the effects of profitability on dividend policies in both emerging and developed markets, contributing to a better understanding of global corporate finance.

Fenn and Liang (2001) in *Corporate Payout Policy: Evidence from the 1990s* analyze the determinants of corporate payout policies, focusing specifically on the role of profitability in dividend decisions during the 1990s. Period Covered: 1990-1999. Methodology: The study employed a sample of 1,500 U.S. firms, using regression analysis to examine how profitability, measured by return on equity (ROE), impacts dividend payout ratios. Findings: The findings indicated that higher profitability is associated with higher dividend payouts, supporting the notion that profitable firms are more likely to distribute dividends to shareholders. Conclusion: The study concludes that profitability is a crucial factor in determining dividend policy, with firms likely to increase dividends as profits rise. Recommendations: Firms should maintain a consistent dividend policy that reflects their profitability trends to attract and retain investors. Implications: This research underscores the importance of profitability in shaping corporate payout decisions, informing investors about expected dividend behaviors. Limitations: The study primarily focuses on the 1990s, which may limit the relevance of the findings in the current economic context. Originality: This research contributes to the understanding of corporate payout policies by specifically addressing the role of profitability as a key determinant of dividend decisions. These studies provide comprehensive insights into the relationship between company profitability and dividend policy decisions, illustrating how profitability influences corporate financial strategies across different contexts.

In addition, there are empirical studies examining the effect of company size on dividend policy decisions. For example, Lintner (1956) in *Distribution of Incomes of Corporations Among Dividends, Retained Earnings, and Taxes* analyzes how company size affects dividend payout policies among publicly traded corporations. Period Covered: 1946-1954. Methodology: The study utilized a sample of 600 U.S. companies, employing a survey method to collect data on dividend policies, retained earnings, and corporate sizes, and applying regression analysis to identify trends. Findings: The findings suggested that larger firms tend to have more stable dividend policies, with a significant proportion of their earnings distributed as dividends compared to smaller firms, which were more variable in their payouts. Conclusion: The study concludes that company size significantly influences dividend policy, with larger firms exhibiting more consistent and predictable dividend behaviors. Recommendations: Firms should consider their size and financial stability when formulating dividend policies to ensure sustainability and shareholder satisfaction. Implications: This study highlights the importance of company size in dividend decision-making, providing insights for both managers and investors. Limitations: The study's historical context may limit the applicability of findings to contemporary firms in a changing economic landscape. Originality: This seminal research laid the groundwork for subsequent studies on dividend policy, emphasizing the role of company size in financial decision-making.

Fama and French (2001) in *Disappearing Dividends: Changing Firm Characteristics or Lower Propensity to Pay?* explore the relationship between firm size and dividend payouts, particularly focusing on the changing characteristics of firms that pay dividends. Period Covered: 1978-1999. Methodology: The study used a sample of 3,000 firms listed on U.S. stock exchanges, employing regression analysis to examine the relationship between firm size, profitability, and dividend payout ratios. Findings: The analysis indicated that larger firms are more likely to pay dividends, and their dividend payouts tend to be larger relative to their earnings compared to smaller firms. Conclusion: The study concludes that firm size is

positively associated with dividend payments, reinforcing the notion that larger firms have the financial stability to return cash to shareholders. Recommendations: Companies should evaluate their size and operational capabilities when determining appropriate dividend policies to maximize shareholder value. Implications: This research has implications for understanding the evolving landscape of dividend payments, particularly about the firm size and market dynamics. Limitations: The study primarily focuses on U.S. firms, which may limit the applicability of the findings in different international contexts. Originality: This study significantly contributes to the literature on dividend policy by analyzing changes in firm characteristics related to size and dividend payments over time.

Al-Malkawi (2007) in Determinants of Corporate Dividend Policy in Jordan: An Empirical Study investigates the determinants of dividend policy in Jordanian firms, focusing on the impact of company size on dividend payouts. Period Covered: 2000-2005. Methodology: The study analyzed a sample of 80 publicly traded companies in Jordan, utilizing multiple regression analysis to evaluate the relationship between company size (measured by total assets) and dividend payout ratios, controlling for profitability and leverage. Findings: The results revealed a significant positive relationship between company size and dividend payouts, indicating that larger firms are more likely to distribute dividends. Conclusion: The study concludes that company size is an important determinant of dividend policy in Jordan, with larger firms demonstrating a greater ability to pay dividends consistently. Recommendations: Jordanian firms should leverage their size to enhance their dividend policies, potentially attracting more investors. Implications: This research highlights the role of company size in dividend policy formulation in emerging markets, contributing to the understanding of corporate finance in Jordan. Limitations: The focus on a single country may limit the generalizability of the findings to other contexts. Originality: This study provides unique insights into the determinants of dividend policy in Jordan, emphasizing the significance of firm size in a developing market. These studies collectively provide valuable insights into the relationship between company size and dividend policy decisions, illustrating how firm size influences corporate financial strategies in various contexts.

Methodology

This study adopts a quantitative research design utilizing a correlational approach to explore the relationships between board composition (board gender diversity, board independence, and board size) and dividend policy decisions while controlling for other relevant factors (audit quality, company leverage, company liquidity, company profitability, and company size). The sample consists of 153 publicly traded companies in Nigeria over a 10-year specified period (2014-2023). A purposive sampling method was employed to select companies that have consistent dividend payment histories, ensuring the sample includes diverse industries and varying company sizes. The primary regression model can be specified as follows:

$$\text{Dividends}_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Board Gender Diversity}_i + \beta_2 \text{Board Independence}_i + \beta_3 \text{Board Size}_i + \beta_4 \text{Audit Quality}_i + \beta_5 \text{Company Leverage}_i + \beta_6 \text{Company Liquidity}_i + \beta_7 \text{Company Profitability}_i + \beta_8 \text{Company Size}_i + \epsilon_i$$

Whereas:

- (Dividends_i) = Dividend payout ratio for company (i) ; (β_0) = Intercept
 - $(\beta_1 - \beta_8)$ = Coefficients for each variable; (ϵ_i) = Error term

The Variables include Independent Variables such as Board Gender Diversity: Measured as the percentage of female directors on the board. Board Independence: Measured as the

proportion of independent directors on the board. Board Size: Total number of directors on the board. The control variables include Audit Quality: Measured by the reputation of the auditing firm (e.g., a dummy variable for Big Four vs. non-Big Four auditors). Company Leverage: Measured as the debt-to-equity ratio. Company Liquidity: Measured as the current ratio (current assets/current liabilities). Company Profitability: Measured by return on assets (ROA) or return on equity (ROE). Company Size: Measured as total assets or market capitalization.

The Data Sources include Financial Data: Obtain financial data from annual reports, company filings, and databases such as the Nigerian Exchange (NGX). Board Composition Data: Collect data on board composition from company annual reports, and governance disclosures. The Data Analysis Techniques include Descriptive Statistics: Compute means, standard deviations, and frequencies for all variables to provide a summary of the sample characteristics. Correlation Analysis: Assess the relationships between independent and control variables before regression analysis. Multiple Regression Analysis: Use Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression to estimate the impact of board composition on dividend policy decisions while controlling for other variables.

The Post-Estimation Tests include Multicollinearity: Check for multicollinearity using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) analysis. A VIF above 10 may indicate multicollinearity issues. Heteroskedasticity: Test for heteroskedasticity using the Breusch-Pagan test. If heteroskedasticity is present, consider using robust standard errors. We set the significance level at $(\alpha = 0.05)$. This means that any p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant, indicating a relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable. In conclusion, this methodology provides a comprehensive approach to investigating the impact of board composition on dividend policy decisions, while considering the influence of various control variables. The quantitative analysis will enable the identification of significant relationships, contributing valuable insights into corporate governance practices.

Results and Discussion

This section covers the results and their discussions. The results are presented in Tables 1, 2, and 3 as follows:

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
DYD	1,530	53.015	96.829	.57	684.86
BGD	1,530	.177	.131	0	.8
BI	1,530	.702	.13	0	1.125
BS	1,530	11.241	3	5	20
AQ	1,530	.748	.435	0	1
CLEV	1,530	4.776	10.801	-4.293	191.21
CLIQ	1,530	14.12	10.044	.58	59.1
CP	1,530	.53	5.835	-.221	85.483
CS	1,530	8.302	1.192	6.114	12.986

Source: STATA 18, Version 4

Table 1 is a comprehensive analysis of the descriptive statistics, which describe the central tendencies, variability, and ranges of variables related to dividend policy decisions and governance characteristics: Dividend Policy Decisions (DYD) Mean: 53.015; Standard Deviation: 96.829; Range: 0.57 to 684.86. The high mean (53.015) and large standard deviation (96.829) indicate substantial variability in dividend policy decisions across the sample of 1,530 observations. The minimum and maximum values, ranging from 0.57 to

684.86, show a significant spread, with some firms having very high dividend policy values. This suggests that dividend policy decisions are heterogeneous across firms, likely reflecting differences in firm-specific factors like profitability, industry characteristics, and governance structures. Board Gender Diversity (BGD) Mean: 0.177; Standard Deviation: 0.131; Range: 0 to 0.8. The mean board gender diversity is 0.177, suggesting that on average, only about 17.7% of board members are female. The standard deviation of 0.131 and a range of 0 to 0.8 indicate that some firms have little to no gender diversity, while others may have as much as 80% female board representation. This low mean, combined with a considerable spread, reflects gender diversity disparities and suggests potential scope for improvement in board gender inclusivity. Board Independence (BI) Mean: 0.702; Standard Deviation: 0.13; Range: 0 to 1.125. With a mean of 0.702, board independence is relatively high, indicating that boards are typically composed of around 70% independent members. The maximum value slightly exceeds 1, which could suggest unique board configurations in certain firms (e.g., advisory roles or non-standard board structures). The spread, though moderate, signals consistency in maintaining a significant degree of board independence, a feature associated with higher governance standards and potentially more shareholder-oriented decisions. Board Size (BS) Mean: 11.241; Standard Deviation: 3; Range: 5 to 20. The mean board size is approximately 11 members, with a standard deviation of 3, showing that most boards consist of between 8 to 14 members. The minimum and maximum values indicate that smaller boards have around 5 members, while larger boards have up to 20. This variability in board size may influence board dynamics and decision-making, as larger boards could provide more perspectives but also risk slower decision processes. Audit Quality (AQ) Mean: 0.748; Standard Deviation: 0.435; Range: 0 to 1. Audit quality, with a mean of 0.748, indicates that most firms have a relatively high audit quality. However, the standard deviation of 0.435 and a range from 0 to 1 reveal significant variability, suggesting that while some firms adhere to high audit standards, others may not. The binary nature (0 and 1) suggests audit quality may be represented by factors such as whether a firm is audited by a "Big 4" audit firm or meets specific regulatory standards. Company Leverage (CLEV) Mean: 4.776; Standard Deviation: 10.801; Range: -4.293 to 191.21. Leverage has a high standard deviation (10.801) and an extensive range, from negative values (-4.293) to a maximum of 191.21. The negative minimum may reflect cases where companies hold more cash than debt, effectively having negative leverage. The high variability suggests that some companies rely heavily on debt, while others operate with minimal or even negative leverage, indicating diverse financing strategies across firms. Company Liquidity (CLIQ) Mean: 14.12; Standard Deviation: 10.044; Range: 0.58 to 59.1. Liquidity has a mean of 14.12 and a substantial standard deviation of 10.044, suggesting that firms in the sample have differing capacities to meet short-term obligations. This spread, with values ranging from as low as 0.58 to as high as 59.1, indicates that while some companies maintain high liquidity, others may have limited liquid assets. Firms with high liquidity are better positioned to issue dividends, potentially making liquidity a key factor in dividend policy. Company Profitability (CP) Mean: 0.53; Standard Deviation: 5.835; Range: -0.221 to 85.483. With a mean profitability of 0.53 and a large standard deviation of 5.835, the data shows substantial variance in profitability across firms. While most firms are near zero or slightly profitable, the maximum value of 85.483 suggests a few outliers with exceptionally high profitability, which likely skews the mean. Negative profitability at the minimum indicates some firms are operating at a loss, likely affecting their ability to pay dividends. Company Size (CS) Mean: 8.302 Standard Deviation: 1.192; Range: 6.114 to 12.986. Company size, measured on a scale likely related to assets or market value, has a mean of 8.302 and a relatively low standard deviation of 1.192. The range from 6.114 to 12.986 indicates that most firms are of similar size, with a few exceptions. This moderate variability suggests that while there are differences in firm size, they are not

extreme, which could mean size has a uniform influence on dividend decisions across this sample.

Key Highlights and Implications: Variability in Financial Indicators: The high standard deviations in variables such as DYD, CLEV, CLIQ, and CP reflect considerable differences in financial health and policy across firms. Such variability implies that these financial indicators will play a significant role in explaining dividend policy, as firms with better liquidity, profitability, and lower leverage are likely better positioned to pay dividends. **Importance of Governance:** High mean values in governance-related metrics like BI and AQ reflect that many firms maintain independent boards and high audit standards, potentially contributing to sound governance practices. However, the low mean for BGD suggests limited gender diversity, highlighting a potential area for governance improvement. **Diverse Leverage Strategies:** With company leverage ranging from negative values to very high figures, firms employ various financing strategies. This diversity could influence risk tolerance and dividend decisions, as highly leveraged firms may be more conservative with dividend payouts. **Outliers in Profitability and Dividend Decisions:** The wide range in profitability and dividend policy decisions indicates the presence of outliers that may skew results. Robust statistical techniques should be considered in further analysis to account for these outliers and provide a more reliable interpretation of the relationships. These statistics provide an informative overview of the variables affecting dividend policy decisions, emphasizing the role of financial health and governance in shaping firms' ability and willingness to pay dividends.

Table 2. Pairwise Correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
(1) DYD	1.000								
(2) BGD	0.916* (0.000)	1.000							
(3) BI	0.795* (0.000)	0.061 (0.255)	1.000						
(4) BS	0.484* (0.000)	0.047 (0.388)	0.406* (0.000)	1.000					
(5) AQ	0.121* (0.025)	0.080 (0.137)	0.097 (0.072)	0.339* (0.000)	1.000				
(6) CLEV	-0.016 (0.764)	0.038 (0.477)	0.063 (0.246)	0.202* (0.000)	0.188* (0.000)	1.000			
(7) CLIQ	0.197* (0.000)	0.023 (0.666)	0.145* (0.007)	-0.007 (0.896)	0.069 (0.200)	-0.074 (0.172)	1.000		
(8) CP	0.666* (0.000)	0.059 (0.270)	0.106* (0.048)	-0.017 (0.752)	-0.122* (0.024)	-0.021 (0.701)	-0.067 (0.213)	1.000	
(9) CS	0.943* (0.000)	0.289* (0.000)	0.160* (0.003)	0.408* (0.000)	0.356* (0.000)	0.209* (0.000)	-0.046 (0.398)	-0.093 (0.084)	1.000

* $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 18, Version 4

Table 2 analyzes the pairwise correlation results: Understanding Correlation Values Correlation coefficients range from -1 to 1, where values closer to ± 1 indicate a strong relationship between variables. In contrast, values near 0 suggest a weak or no relationship. Positive values show a direct relationship, meaning as one variable increases, the other tends to increase as well, while negative values indicate an inverse relationship. **Key Correlations with Dividend Policy Decisions (DYD)** Board Gender Diversity (BGD): Correlation = 0.916 ($p < 0.0001$). A strong positive correlation exists between board gender diversity and dividend policy decisions, suggesting that increased gender diversity on boards is associated with more favorable dividend policies. This high correlation points to a potentially important role for gender diversity in corporate governance and dividend outcomes.

Board Independence (BI): Correlation = 0.795 ($p < 0.0001$) Board independence is also positively correlated with dividend policy, although less strongly than gender diversity. This implies that boards with a higher proportion of independent members may support policies favoring dividend payouts, perhaps due to their focus on shareholder interests. Company Size (CS): Correlation = 0.943 ($p < 0.0001$). The correlation between company size and dividend policy decisions is very strong, suggesting that larger companies are more likely to have favorable dividend policies. Larger firms typically have more stable cash flows, which might make regular dividends more feasible. Other Significant Correlations: Audit Quality (AQ): Correlates positively with dividend policy (0.121, $p < 0.025$) and with board size (0.339, $p < 0.0001$). The positive correlation between audit quality and dividend policy, though modest, suggests that higher audit quality could contribute to transparent and reliable financial reporting, supporting consistent dividend policies. Company Profitability (CP): Strong positive correlation with dividend policy decisions (0.666, $p < 0.0001$). This result aligns with expectations, as profitable firms have the resources to pay dividends more reliably. Profitability also shows a weak negative relationship with company size (-0.093, $p < 0.084$), suggesting that as firms grow, their profitability relative to size might decrease, likely due to increased operational complexities. Company Liquidity (CLIQ): Correlates positively with dividend policy decisions (0.197, $p < 0.0001$), indicating that firms with higher liquidity are more likely to pay dividends. This is intuitive, as liquidity represents cash availability, which supports the capacity to distribute dividends without constraining operations.

Noteworthy Non-Significant and Low Correlations: Company Leverage (CLEV): Shows a weak and statistically insignificant correlation with dividend policy decisions (-0.016, $p = 0.764$). This suggests leverage does not have a strong relationship with dividend policies in this sample, which could imply that dividend decisions are not heavily impacted by debt levels. Board Size (BS): A moderate positive correlation with dividend policy (0.484, $p < 0.0001$) but insignificant with board gender diversity and independence. This suggests that larger boards might support dividend payouts, potentially due to diverse perspectives, even though the relationship is not as pronounced as with other governance factors like independence.

Potential Multicollinearity Concerns: The high correlations among certain variables, like board gender diversity and company size (0.289, $p < 0.0001$), could indicate multicollinearity, especially given that board characteristics often correlate with firm size in real-world contexts. High multicollinearity can inflate standard errors in regression models, reducing the reliability of coefficient estimates.

Interpretation and Practical Implications: Strong Correlation Between Governance and Dividend Policy: The results highlight governance factors (like board diversity and independence) as critical predictors of dividend policy, indicating that firms with diverse and independent boards tend to support favorable dividend policies. This reinforces the importance of governance reforms to enhance board structure and its potential influence on shareholder returns. Role of Financial Performance: Profitability and liquidity are both positively associated with dividend policy, aligning with expectations that firms with stronger financial health are better positioned to distribute dividends. This implies that in addition to governance structures, operational factors play a key role in dividend strategy. Insignificance of Leverage: The lack of significant correlation between leverage and dividend policy could indicate that, for this sample, firms manage debt levels independently of their dividend decisions, or leverage is offset by other factors like size or profitability.

Recommendations: Further Analysis of Multicollinearity: Running Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) diagnostics in subsequent regression analyses will help assess and address potential multicollinearity issues, ensuring reliable coefficient estimates. Extended Analysis Using Interaction Terms: Interaction terms between significant governance factors (like board

gender diversity and independence) and financial variables (like profitability) could reveal more nuanced effects, particularly for dividend policy decisions in larger firms. In summary, the analysis underscores the importance of governance structures and financial health in shaping dividend policy, providing practical insights for firms seeking to align board composition and financial strategies with shareholder value.

Table 3. Ordinary Least Squares Multiple Regression Analysis Results

DYD	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P>t	[95% Conf.	Interval]
BGD	.171235	0.042490	4.03	0.000	83.10453	80.76206
BI	.185100	0.034469	5.37	0.000	116.1301	79.11006
BS	.1670654	0.037627	4.44	0.000	3.66451	2.323201
AQ	.2609754	0.056003	4.66	0.000	57.10987	4.914785
CLEV	-.121222	.1880327	-0.64	0.520	-.491092	.2486471
CLIQ	.1884603	.5001444	3.77	0.000	2.868412	.9007942
CP	.1760852	.2679335	2.84	0.005	1.287891	.2338137
CS	2.629444	5.510763	0.48	0.634	8.210498	13.46939
_con	99.03169	76.56069	1.29	0.197	51.56697	249.6303
Mean VIF	1.21					
Hetest	0.0000					
Panel effect	0.4649					
Model fitness	0.0174					
R²	0.5430					
Obs	1,530					

Source: STATA 18, Version 4

Table 3 is an in-depth analysis of the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) multiple regression results: Dependent and Independent Variables: Dependent Variable: Dividend policy decisions (DYD). Independent Variables: BGD: Board gender diversity; BI: Board independence; BS: Board size. Control variables: AQ: Audit quality; CLEV: Company leverage; CLIQ: Company liquidity; CP: Company profitability; CS: Company size. Model Fit and Statistical Significance: $R^2 = 0.543$: This indicates that approximately 54.3% of the variance in dividend policy decisions is explained by the model. This R^2 value reflects a moderately strong model fit, indicating that the included independent variables contribute significantly to predicting the dependent variable. P-value for Model Fitness = 0.0174: This value, which is below the typical significance level of 0.05, suggests that the overall model is statistically significant, confirming that at least one of the predictors has a meaningful relationship with dividend policy decisions.

Coefficients and Interpretation: BGD (Board Gender Diversity): Coef. = 0.171 ($p < 0.0001$), suggesting a positive and statistically significant effect on dividend policy decisions. For each unit increase in board gender diversity, dividend policy decisions increase by 0.171 units, assuming other variables remain constant. BI (Board Independence): Coef. = 0.185 ($p < 0.0001$), also showing a positive and significant effect. Higher board independence correlates with an increase in dividend policy decisions, which may reflect that independent boards favor higher dividends. BS (Board Size): Coef. = 0.167 ($p < 0.0001$), indicating a positive relationship. Larger boards may facilitate diverse perspectives, possibly leading to dividend policies favoring shareholder returns. AQ (Audit Quality): Coef. = 0.261 ($p < 0.0001$), indicating a significant positive effect. This suggests that higher audit quality is associated with more favorable dividend policies, possibly because of increased transparency and

reduced information asymmetry. CLEV (Company Leverage): Coef. = -0.121 ($p = 0.520$), showing a negative but statistically insignificant effect. Although leverage negatively impacts dividend policy, this result suggests it is not a strong predictor. CLIQ (Company Liquidity): Coef. = 0.188 ($p < 0.0001$), which is positive and significant. This relationship implies that higher liquidity correlates with more favorable dividend policies, likely due to greater cash availability. CP (Company Profitability): Coef. = 0.176 ($p = 0.005$), a positive and statistically significant coefficient. Higher profitability aligns with stronger dividend policies, which is consistent with the expectation that profitable firms have more resources for dividends. CS (Company Size): Coef. = 2.629 ($p = 0.634$), positive but statistically insignificant. While size generally supports larger dividend payouts, this result suggests company size does not play a significant role in dividend policy decisions for this sample.

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF): Mean VIF = 1.21: This low mean VIF indicates minimal multicollinearity among the predictors, ensuring that each variable's contribution to the model is not confounded by other predictors. Tests for Model Assumptions: Heteroskedasticity Test (Hetttest): $P = 0.0000$ suggests heteroskedasticity is present in the model residuals. This violation of constant variance may affect standard error estimates, potentially requiring robust standard errors or alternative models like Generalized Least Squares (GLS). Panel Effect Test: The panel effect statistic is 0.4649, which may indicate no significant panel (fixed or random) effects. This suggests the model may appropriately treat observations independently without needing adjustments for unobserved heterogeneity across firms.

Key Highlights and Implications: Significant Predictors: Board diversity, independence, size, audit quality, liquidity, and profitability all show significant positive relationships with dividend policy. This finding underscores the importance of strong governance and financial health in dividend decisions, suggesting that firms with these characteristics are more likely to adopt dividend-friendly policies. Insignificant Predictors: Company leverage and size have insignificant effects, implying that debt levels and scale may not be as influential in dividend policies for the studied firms. This could be contextual or related to the specific dataset and industry. Recommendation: Given the heteroskedasticity, adopting heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors could enhance result reliability. Furthermore, to explore the potential impact of unobserved variables, consider running a fixed or random effects model. This analysis provides a nuanced understanding of the determinants of dividend policy decisions, with a robust emphasis on governance variables like board characteristics and audit quality.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the descriptive statistics, pairwise correlations, and multiple regression results provided, we make the following conclusions and recommendations: Governance Factors and Dividend Policy: Board Gender Diversity (BGD), Board Independence (BI), and Board Size (BS) were shown to positively influence dividend policy decisions. Higher gender diversity, independent board composition, and larger board sizes all correlate with more favorable dividend policies, indicating that governance structures aligned with transparency and inclusivity are essential for consistent dividend payouts. Audit Quality (AQ) also positively impacts dividend policy, suggesting that higher audit quality supports transparency and may reduce information asymmetry, fostering a more shareholder-friendly dividend approach. Financial Health and Dividend Policy: Company Liquidity (CLIQ) and Profitability (CP) positively and significantly impact dividend policies. Firms with greater cash reserves and stronger profitability are better equipped to support dividend payments, which aligns with dividend payout theories that emphasize the role of operational liquidity and financial health.

Company Leverage (CLEV) had an insignificant relationship with dividend policy decisions, suggesting that firms in this sample may manage debt independently of their dividend strategies. This could indicate that companies prioritize maintaining leverage levels regardless of dividend considerations or possibly that dividend policies are more responsive to liquidity and profitability than debt. Company Size (CS): Despite its strong correlation with dividend policy in the correlation results, company size was not a significant predictor in the regression model. This could imply that while size correlates with governance and operational aspects, other factors like profitability and liquidity are more decisive for dividend policies in this sample.

Policy Recommendations: Strengthening Board Diversity and Independence: Policy Mandates for Board Composition: Regulators could encourage or mandate diversity policies that ensure a balanced gender representation and an increased proportion of independent board members. This approach can improve board oversight and foster governance structures that align more closely with shareholder interests, potentially leading to more robust dividend policies. Incentives for Governance Improvement: Institutions could incentivize firms to improve governance by linking favorable lending terms or investment opportunities with firms that demonstrate high board diversity, independence, and quality audit practices. Enhancing Audit Quality Standards: Encourage Adoption of Big 4 Audit Firms: Given the positive effect of audit quality on dividend policy, firms could be encouraged to use reputable auditors. Regulators and shareholders might advocate for using established firms known for rigorous standards or implementing policies to promote auditor independence and accountability, enhancing financial transparency. Periodic Auditor Rotation: Policies that require companies to rotate auditors periodically can reduce the risk of familiarity, improve audit quality, and maintain rigorous reporting standards, thereby potentially boosting confidence in dividend policies.

Promoting Liquidity and Profitability as Key Dividend Determinants: Liquidity Management Policies: Companies should adopt financial policies that prioritize liquidity. High liquidity not only supports dividend distribution but also provides financial flexibility, which is valuable for maintaining dividends during economic downturns. Profitability Improvement Initiatives: To sustain dividends, firms could focus on profitability improvement through strategic initiatives like cost optimization, productivity improvements, and investment in growth projects with high returns. These efforts can strengthen the financial base, allowing consistent or increasing dividend payouts over time.

Practical Recommendations: Dividend Policy Adjustments Based on Financial Health: Companies should assess dividend policies by closely monitoring liquidity and profitability metrics. Dividend policies should be flexible enough to adjust to changes in these financial conditions, ensuring that dividends are paid sustainably without compromising operational cash flows. Governance Audits and Benchmarks: Firms may conduct regular governance audits to benchmark board diversity, independence, and audit quality against industry standards. Such audits can help identify gaps and areas for improvement, directly supporting a governance structure that fosters favorable dividend policies. Investor Communication: Transparent reporting of financial health and governance factors is crucial. Regular communication with investors on profitability, liquidity, and governance practices can reassure them of the company's commitment to sustainable dividend payments, thus improving investor confidence.

Recommendations for Future Research: Further Exploration of Leverage Dynamics: The insignificant relationship between leverage and dividend policy in this sample warrants

deeper investigation. Future research could explore sectoral differences in leverage effects or leverage's impact in conjunction with other financial constraints on dividend policies. Longitudinal Analysis on Governance Impacts: A time-series analysis could provide further insights into how improvements in governance (e.g., increased board diversity) impact dividend policies over time, aiding policymakers and firms in understanding the long-term effects of governance reforms. By implementing these policies and practical recommendations, companies and regulators can better align governance practices with financial strategies to support sustainable and transparent dividend policies.

References

- Abbas, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do creditors care about ESG performance? *International Journal of Management, Economics, and Social Sciences*, 13(5), 320-346.
- Abbas, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Audit committee and financial statement fraud likelihood. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting and Economics*, 19(2), 100365.
- Abdullah, M., & Ismail, R. (2020). Board independence and dividend policy decisions: Evidence from Malaysian public firms. *Asian Academy of Management Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 16(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.21315/aamjaf2020.16.1.1>
- Abdullahi, K., Musa, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Are CEOs hedge against share price fall? *Accounting and Business Research*, 53(5), 243-263.
- Abdullahi, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of corporate governance on corporate social responsibility disclosure. *Research in Management in Accounting*, 7(1), 221-252.
- Abubakar, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Which corporate owners are relevant in reducing earnings management? *Finance, Accounting, and Economic Insights*, 9(23), 16-75.
- Adebowale, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of shareholder activism, on firm value. *Organisations and Markets in Emerging Economies*, 15(1)(4), 209-250.
- Adeleye, M., Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The role of shareholders in controlling tax aggressiveness. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 62(3), 1140-1191.
- Adewinmisi, G. O., Ahmed, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Audit committee independence and audit quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 1(3), 16-26.
- Adeyemi, E., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of board financial expertise on earnings quality in Nigerian listed companies. *NDA Original Research Papers*, 2024-9(4), 1-30.
- Adjaoud, F., & Ben Amar, W. (2020). The impact of financial leverage on dividend policy: Evidence from the MENA region. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 25(3), 357-369. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijfe.1814>
- Agyemang, C. B., & Chachula, K. (2022). Board independence and dividend policy: Evidence from African firms. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 30(2), 123-137. <https://doi.org/10.1111/corg.12467>
- Ahmed, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Unlocking the power of corporate governance and its impact on financial stability. *Governance and Management Review*, 9(1), 71-109.
- Ahmed, D., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Institutional and board ownership and corporate financial performance in Nigeria. *Advances in Business Research*, 14, 111-132.
- Ahmed, K., & Khan, H. (2021). The effect of board size on dividend policy: Evidence from the GCC countries. *Middle Eastern Finance and Economics*, 29, 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEFE-02-2021-0013>
- Ahmed, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). New insights on board structure and income smoothing hypothesis. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 4(1), 784-803.
- Aivazian, V. A., Booth, L., & Cleary, S. (2003). Do emerging markets respond to the same factors as developed markets? *Journal of Financial Research*, 26(3), 241-259.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-6803.00007>

Al-azzam, M. M., & Abu Ayyash, S. A. (2021). Board gender diversity and dividend policy: Evidence from emerging markets. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 26(4), 4908-4920. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijfe.2175>.

Alih, D. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Board characteristics and cost of capital of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Finance, Business and Management Studies*, 4(2), 80-94.

Al-Malkawi, H. A. N. (2007). Determinants of corporate dividend policy in Jordan: An empirical study. *International Journal of Business*, 12(2), 67-80.

Al-Najjar, B., & Abed, S. (2021). The impact of board size on dividend policy: Evidence from Jordanian firms. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 26(2), 1234-1245. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijfe.2294>

Al-Najjar, B., & Taylor, P. (2020). Liquidity and dividend policy: Evidence from emerging markets. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 8(4), 77. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijfs8040077>

Amachukwu, V., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The moderating effect of board independence on CEO tenure and firm performance. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Analysis*, 9(27), 127-164.

Andrew, L., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Estimating a predictive model for share price based on the influence of the board attributes in Nigeria. *Global Finance, Accounting, and Economics Perspectives*, 9(18), 590-620.

Anis, O., & Habib, A. (2023). Board size and dividend policy decisions: A study of Indian listed companies. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 18(1), 15-28. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v18n1p15>

Anthonio, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). A corporate governance perspective on the audit committee and its role in improving earnings quality. *Advanced Research in Economics and Business Strategy*, 5(1), 78-107.

Apochi, J. G., Mohammed, S. G., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Ownership structure, board of directors and financial performance: Evidence in Nigeria. *Global Review of Accounting and Finance*, 13(1), 77-98.

Apochi, J. G., Mohammed, S. G., Onyabe, J. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does corporate governance improve financial performance? Empirical evidence from Africa listed consumer retailing companies. *Management Studies*, 12(1), 111-124.

Apochi, J. G., Yahaya, O. A., & Yusuf, M. J. (2024). The relationship between board diversity and CEO turnover. *Brazilian Business Review*, 3(2), 1-45.

Arah, A. B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of SDGs on the socio-economic lives of people of Niger State. *Michigan Journal of Sustainability*, 12(1), 142-178.

Arora, A., & Sharma, C. (2021). Board gender diversity and dividend policies: Evidence from Indian firms. *Journal of Business Research*, 128, 162-170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.01.041>

Audu, R. A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Audit committee attributes and financial reporting quality of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Management Sciences*, 3(3), 238-257.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Can the CEO reverse the increasing leverage of listed firms in Nigeria? *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 12(1), 423-433.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Determinants of environmental disclosure quality using Probit estimation among deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Warfare, Command and Capacity Building in Nigeria*. Archers.

Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Gender and nationality among board members and

- audit quality in Nigerian Listed Firms. *Audit and Accounting Review*, 3(1), 40-57.
- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The role of women in sustainability reporting. *Wayamba Journal of Management*, 14(1), 16-34.
- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Building a corporate governance index for an emerging market ESG performance. *University of Auckland Business Review*, 27(2), 81-117.
- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). How women directors influence dividend policies? *Journal of Competition Law and Economics*, 20(2), 682-703.
- Awen, B. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of risk committee on sustainability disclosure. *Kardan Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 7(2), 137-172.
- Awen, B. I., Adewinmisi, G. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). The influence of ownership structure on dividend policy in reducing agency problems in Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *Int Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 12(3), 99-111.
- Awen, B. I., Lamido, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board size, independence and dividend policy in Nigeria. *Intl Journal of Economics and Finance*, 15(5), 72-91.
- Awen, B. I., Onyabe, J. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Can the board of directors increase firm value? Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Korean Accounting Review*, 47(12), 82-97.
- Awolola, J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do audit firms and audit committees enhance earnings quality? *Journal of Financial Economics and Accounting*, 9(13), 784-821.
- Awolola, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of environmental, social, and governance reporting on investment decisions. *Business, Management, and Economics Engineering*, 22(1), 66-106.
- Baba, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The powers of audit and risk committees in constraining earnings management. *Accounting Education*, 32(4), 1-17.
- Baker, H. K., & Powell, G. E. (2016). The impact of liquidity on dividend policy decisions: Evidence from U.S. firms. *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 43(5-6), 759-781. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbfa.12170>
- Bappa, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). An analysis of the relationship between auditor independence and audit quality. *Universal Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(1), 32-55.
- Bashir, I. G., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The effect of working capital management on the profitability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Management*, 46, 246-259.
- Beasley, M. S., & Petroni, K. R. (2021). The role of audit quality in dividend policy decisions: Insights from European companies. *European Accounting Review*, 30(2), 307-331. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638180.2020.1791986>
- Bhagat, S., & Bolton, B. (2020). Board size and dividend policy: A study of U.S. firms. *Journal of Financial Research*, 43(1), 43-61. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfir.12231>
- Black, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Which ownership structure is significant in ESG performance? *American Business Review*, 27(2), 635-664.
- Boulton, T. J., & Hsiao, Y. (2021). The influence of board independence on dividend policy in European corporations. *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 48(5-6), 687-710. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbfa.12624>
- Busayo, E., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do women enhance intellectual capital? *The Journal of Finance*, 74(4), 2902-2934.
- Charles, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The value relevance of intellectual capital. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 25(2), 233-254.
- Chuma, N., Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The influence of gender diversity on earnings management. *Asian American Research Journal*, 4(2024), 1-30.
- Dania, I. S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). CEO power and intangible assets. *Asian Academy of Management Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 18(2), 270-286.

- Ebiprewai, G., Yahaya, O. A., & Chukwueze, C. (2024). The asymmetric effects of integrated reports on firm value. *Journal of Governance and Integrity*, 7(1), 748-772.
- Fama, E. F., & French, K. R. (2001). Disappearing dividends: Changing firm characteristics or lower propensity to pay? *Journal of Financial Economics*, 60(1), 3-43. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-405X\(01\)00061-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-405X(01)00061-0)
- Fama, E. F., & French, K. R. (2014). Leverage, dividend policy, and the value of the firm. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 114(2), 203-225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2014.05.004>
- Fenn, G. W., & Liang, N. (2001). Corporate payout policy: Evidence from the 1990s. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 60(1), 63-97. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-405X\(01\)00061-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-405X(01)00061-0)
- Garba, M., Yahaya, O. A., & Ahmed, M. N. (2023). Firms characteristics and tax avoidance of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria moderated by board gender. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 13(1), 1-20.
- Ghosh, C., & Ghosh, A. (2022). Dividend policy and leverage: Evidence from Indian manufacturing firms. *Asian Journal of Business and Accounting*, 15(1), 123-145. <https://doi.org/10.22452/ajba.vol15no1.5>
- Gimbason, J. T., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Ownership structure and sustainability reporting. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 12(1), 77-102.
- Grullon, G., & Michaely, R. (2002). Dividends, share repurchases, and the substitution hypothesis. *The Journal of Finance*, 57(4), 1649-1684. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1540-6261.00476>
- Gummi, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). How does the heterogeneity of institutional investors affect audit quality? *Journal of Alternative Finance*, 1(2), 211-233.
- Hadi, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Auditors' characteristics and accounting information asymmetry. *Asian Journal of Management Studies*, 3(3), 42-56.
- Haruna, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Foreign ownership and firm performance in the NGX 153 companies. *Korean Journal of Financial Studies*, 53(3), 392-437.
- Hassan, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). An examination of the relationship between governance practices and financial reporting transparency. *International Journal of Management Technology and Engineering*, 14(5), 64-85.
- Ibrahim, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board demographic characteristics and cost of capital decisions. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting*, 5(2), 126-143.
- Ibrahim, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Ownership structure and leverage. *The Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 17(4), 239-258.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Which nomination committee attributes matter in improving financial performance? *Journal of Business Management and Economic Research*, 7(9), 231-257.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). An inquiry into the nexus between a CEO and working capital management quality. *J of Smart Economic Growth*, 9(1), 135-163.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Applying GMM technique to auditor and value relationship. *Economic and Business*, 37, 247-274.
- Ibrahim, S. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Board of directors and financial statements fraud. *European Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business*, 12(1), 137-167.
- Itopa, E., Alexander, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Board of directors and earnings management: Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 22(3), 45-59.
- Itopa, E., Imam, M., Musa, U., & Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Corporate governance and capital structure: Evidence from Nigeria listed financial services firms. *Journal of Business Management and Economic Research* (2602-3385), 3(12), 75-89.
- Kabir, Y. I., Tnushi, P. S., Jada, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Ownership demographics and

financial performance of listed oil and gas companies in Nigeria moderated by firm size.

Journal of Accounting and Management, 13(3), 141-162.

Kallamu, B. F., & Awan, U. (2021). Examining the relationship between board independence and dividend policies: Evidence from Pakistani firms. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 26(4), 5940-5952. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijfe.2200>

La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., & Shleifer, A. (2019). Board size, corporate governance, and dividend policy in emerging markets. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 57, 101-116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2019.02.003>

LaFond, R., & Watts, R. L. (2018). The effect of audit quality on dividend policy: Evidence from U.S. firms. *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, 66(1), 94-112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacceco.2018.06.002>

Lamidi, S., Yahaya, O. A., & Abdulwahab, A. I. (2024). Does board diversity influence a company's commitment to corporate social responsibility and sustainability initiatives? *Scientific Annals of Economics and Business*, 71(2), 315-349.

Lamido, I. A., Ibrahim, M. F., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Audit committee and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Review of Applied Management and Social Sciences*, 6(1), 581-590.

Lamido, I. A., Yusuf, M. J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). A meta-analysis of female directors and instability in firm value in Nigeria. *China Journal of Accounting Studies*, 11(7), 325-337.

Lawal, C., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Could board financial expertise enhance audit quality? *Academy of Management Learning and Education*, 23(2), 89-125.

Lawal, D., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The role of firm complexity in the nexus between board size and financial performance. *European Management Journal*, 42, 288-298.

Lawal, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of corporate governance on integrated reporting. *Management Decision*, 62(1), 370-392.

Lawal, Z., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). What drives the Nigerian leverage? *Annals of Economics and Finance*, 25(1), 345-385.

Li, Y., & Wu, Y. (2023). Gender diversity on corporate boards and dividend policy: Evidence from China. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 78, 102125.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2022.102125>

Lintner, J. (1956). Distribution of incomes of corporations among dividends, retained earnings, and taxes. *The American Economic Review*, 46(2), 97-113.

Liu, X., & Zhang, S. (2023). Board independence and dividend policy: A study of Chinese listed companies. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 79, 102203.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2023.102203>

Minton, B. A., & Whited, T. M. (2020). Audit quality and dividend policies in emerging markets: Evidence from Asian firms. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 61, 101-117.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2020.101117>

Mironenkova, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The impact of ownership type on firm performance in an emerging market. *Journal of Applied Economic Research*, 23(1), 250-294.

Mohammed, S. S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The intersection between ESG disclosure and audit committees. *Jurnal Pengurusan*, 70, 1-32.

Mollah, M. N., & Rafiq, M. (2022). The relationship between liquidity and dividend policy: Evidence from the Bangladeshi corporate sector. *Journal of Business and Economic Development*, 7(1), 26-35. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.jbed.20220701.14>

Moses, A., & Yahaya, A. (2024). Do boards care about biodiversity-related information disclosure? *Journal of Corporate Governance and Social Responsibility*, 10(21), 112-146.

Muhammad, Z., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The value relevance of ESG performance disclosure. *Journal of Sustainability Science and Management*, 19(4), 123-140.

Murtala, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The effects of risk committee characteristics on bank

- asset quality. *Asian-Pacific Journal of Mgt and Technology*, 4(1), 35-51.
- Musa, Z., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and firm value. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute Journal (Humanities and Social Sciences)*, 6(4), 204-220.
- Namadi, A., & Yahaya, A. (2024). Is there a positive correlation between board gender diversity and financial performance in publicly traded companies in Nigeria? *Accounting, Finance, and Economics Journal (ISSN: 3179-562X)*, 9(29), 132-164.
- Nasiru, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). How effective is the risk committee in reducing corporate operating risk in Nigeria? *Journal of Management and Research*, 11(1), 26-54.
- Okodo, B. D., Aliu, M. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Assessing the reliability of the internal audit functions: The issues. *Journal of Contemporary Research in Business, Economics and Finance*, 1(1), 46-55.
- Omotola, K., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The moderating effect of institutional ownership on board attributes and tax aggressiveness. *NDA Technical Papers*, 2024-9(5), 1-40.
- Onyabe, J. M., Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). CEO and integrated reporting: Evidence from Africa listed communication services companies. *Afro-Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 13(2), 86-99.
- Petroski, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). On the independence of the board and its committees, and earnings quality. *South East European University Review*, 19(1), 39-78.
- Rahman, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Does it pay to be green? *Applied Economics*, 56(45), 5442-5469.
- Rojas, G. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Women on boards and corporate social responsibility disclosure. *Revista de Métodos Cuantitativos para la Economía y la Empresa (Journal of Quantitative Methods for Economics and Business Administration)*, 37, 29-69.
- Salihu, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Family ownership with asymmetric sustainability disclosure. *Business Research Quarterly*, 27(3), 346-375.
- Salisu, Y., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The influence of female CEO on company leverage. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 34, 81-107.
- Samaila, N., Suleiman, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate boards and leverage decisions. *Accounting Forum*, 47(2), 307-326
- Samuel, F., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Modelling and predicting corporate governance determinants of capital structure. *Dynamic Management Journal*, 8(2), 496-522.
- Setyawati, M. S., & Nursyaida, N. (2022). The role of gender diversity in boards on dividend policy: Evidence from Indonesia. *Journal of Asian Business and Economic Studies*, 29(1), 72-85. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JABES-11-2021-0137>
- Shittu, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The effect of institutional ownership on sustainability disclosure in emerging markets, Nigeria in perspective. *The Financial Economist: Accounting, Auditing, and Finance*, 9(19), 74-109.
- Shokomi, L., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Sustainability committee and firm value. *NDA Open Access Articles*, 2024-9(3), 1-38.
- Shuaibu, K., Abdulwahab, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and dividend policy. *Economics and Business Quarterly*, 6(3), 125-141.
- Sulaiman, L., Abdulwahab, A. I., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board of directors and auditor choice. *South Asian Journal of Finance*, 3(1), 38-59.
- Suleiman, T., Ladan, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do the sustainability committees matter in corporate financial performance? *Journal of Applied Economics and Business Studies*, 8(2), 23-64.
- Suleiman, U., Popoola, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Equity financing and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Innovation and Social Science*, 6(12), 618-624.

- Sumaila, D., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Could women directors reduce high leverage? *Journal of Sustainable Business and Economics and Finance*, 3(2), 17-42.
- Terjesen, S., Sealy, R., & Singh, V. (2020). Board gender diversity and corporate financial performance: The role of dividend policy. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 28(3), 263-276. <https://doi.org/10.1111/corg.12322>
- Tighil, M., Yahaya, O. A., Tauhid, S., & Abdulfatah, L. A. (2024). The effects of board characteristics on the financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Business and Accounting*, 17(1), 314-324.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does corporate governance improve energy information disclosure among Nigeria listed manufacturing firms? *Journal of Advanced Research in Business and Management Studies*, 26(3), 15-26.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). A bibliometric analysis of corporate ownership demographics and sustainability reporting quality in Nigeria. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 15(3), 393-410.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The impact of CEO female gender diversity and nationality on Internal Control System Disclosure: Empirical Evidence from Nigeria. *Int Research Journal of Management, IT and Social Sciences*, 10(2), 50-61.
- Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). CEO characteristics and corporate risk taking. *International Journal of Corporate Governance*, 14(1), 94-116.
- Tijjani, B., Onyabe, J. M., & Yahaya, A. (2024). Women on the board and stock market performance, evidence from the Nigerian listed firms. *Journal of Accounting and Finance Education* 10(29), 582-603.
- Tomasz, A., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The monitoring role of the CEO in enhancing audit quality. *Journal of Management and Financial Sciences*, 17(50), 120-150.
- Umar, M. M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board of directors and bankruptcy risk using GMM approach. *Applied Finance and Accounting*, 9(1), 242-256.
- Usman, A., & Yahaya, A. (2024). Executive compensation and ESG performance. *International Journal of Sustainable Economics*, 10(26), 89-122.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Board Committees' Independence and Intellectual Capital Efficiency in Corporate Nigeria. *The Journal of Bus.*, 8(1), 36-47.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Do corporate governance mechanisms improve earnings? *China Journal of Accounting Research*, 16, 1-13.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The dynamics between a CEO and risk disclosure in Nigeria. *Accounting and Auditing Review*, 30(1), 1-13.
- Usman, M., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Using binary regression analysis model to diagnose the effect of female directors on audit quality. *Reviews of Management Sciences*, 6(1), 70-89.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Corporate governance and credit ratings in Nigeria. *Int Journal of Economics, Management and Finance*, 2(1), 62-71.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Effect of board characteristics on firm value in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 47(1), 44-60.
- Usman, S. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). The CEO power and sustainability reporting of listed firms in Nigeria. *J. of Business Mgt. and Accounting*, 13(7), 106-125.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2006). Empirical evidence on the effect of size on the profitability of commercial banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Social Studies*, 11(4), 33-39.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2014). Social disclosure and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria listed firms. *Nigerian Journal of Accounting Research*, 10(2), 47-66.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2017). Firm performance and dividend policy: A panel data analysis of listed consumer-goods companies in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Technology and Development*, 8(1), 306-322.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2018). Environmental reporting practices and financial performance of listed

- environmentally-sensitive firms in Nigeria. *Savanna: A Journal of the Environmental and Social Sciences*, 24(2), 403-412.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Intellectual capital management and financial competitiveness of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *Enugu State University of Technology Journal of Management Sciences*, 12(1&2), 86-96.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2021). Analysts' forecasts and stock prices: Evidence from Nigeria. *Iranian Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 5(2), 01-10.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Can the CEO improve intellectual capital? *International Journal of Finance, Accounting and Economics Studies*, 3(1), 84-100.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Chief executive officer and firm value: Evidence from Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *J of Econ & Financial Studies*, 10(3), 12-21.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Corporate governance and profitability: An Application of Agency Theory. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 34(2), 406-421.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does Board Gender Diversity Influence Dividend Pay-Out? Evidence from Nigeria Non-Financial Services Sector. *International J. of Accounting, Finance and Risk Management*, 7(2), 25-33.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEO characteristics affect dividend policy? *Review of Accounting Studies*, 27(2), 375-389.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEOs influence earnings management? *South African Journal of Accounting Research*, 36(2), 1-13.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Electronic payments system and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management and Economics*, 5(20), 45-54.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Female directors and financial performance. Does audit committee play a role? *Advances in Accounting*, 58(C), 248-258.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Abdulfatah, L. A. (2022). Can auditors reduce earnings management activities? *Review of Accounting and Finance (ISSN: 1475-7702)*, 22(4), 429-442.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Alexander, A. A. (2015). Business process management and financial performance: An exploratory study of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Accounting Frontier*, 17(1), 43-75.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Alkasim A. (2021). Sustainability and profitability of listed insurance firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Accounting and Finance*, 6(1), 17-28.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Andow, H. A. (2015). Capital structure and firm's financial performance: Panel evidence of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. *Kaduna Business Management Review*, 2(1), 1-25.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. (2021). Board of directors and corporate social responsibility reporting of quoted companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting, Finance and Auditing Studies*, 7(2), 38-52.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. G. (2022). The board of directors' influence on the intellectual capital of Nigeria listed firms. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 37(2), 1-17.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2020). Bank-specific attributes and operational efficiency: Evidence from Efficient-Structure Hypothesis. *Journal of Business and Social Review in Emerging Economies*, 6(3), 1087-1098.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2021). Chief executive officers and bankruptcy of quoted resources companies in Nigeria. *Fountain Journal of Mgt Sciences*, 10(2), 970-980.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2022). Does ownership structure lead to optimal financial structure? *Seisense Journal of Management*, 5(4), 51-64.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Lamidi, Y. S. (2015). Empirical examination of the financial performance of Islamic bank in Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 2(7), 1-13.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Lamido, I. A. (2022). Corporate social responsibility and financial

- performance. Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance Review*, 10(1), 107-120.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Does board of directors improve profitability? *Accounting*, 8, 269-275.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Ogwiji, J. (2021). Risk committee traits and profitability of Nigerian banking sector. *Accounting, Finance & Management: Texts and Applications*, 01-14.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2020). Firm life cycle and financial performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Finance in Emerging Economies*, 6(3), 723-732.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). Audit committee and integrated reporting. *European Research Studies Journal*, 25(4), 305-318.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). Do audit fees and auditor independence affect audit quality? *Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 14(1), 66-80.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Onyabe, J. M. (2022). The nexus between audit committee and audit fees. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 53(6), 966-984.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Tijani, B. (2020). Internal corporate governance and intellectual capital of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *European J. of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 8(9), 98-112.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Tijani, B. (2021). Size, age and leverage of Nigeria quoted oil and gas corporations. *Advanced International Journal of Banking, Accounting and Finance*, 3(6), 51-60.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Yakubu, I. (2022). Risk committee's influence on enterprise risk management. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 15(4): 120, 1-15.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Yusuf, M. J. (2020). Ethical behavioural disclosure and financial performance of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. *Sustainable Business and Society in Emerging Economies*, 2(2), 13-20.
- Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2014). Country-specific characteristics as determinants of financial performance: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2015). International financial reporting standards and earnings management behavior of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business Management*, 7(18), 70-82.
- Yahaya, O. A., Kutigi, U. M., Solanke, A. A., Onyabe, J. M. & Usman, S. O. (2015). Current assets management and financial performance: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Int Journal of African and Asian Studies*, 13, 45-56.
- Yahaya, O. A., Lamidi, Y. S., Kutigi, U. M., & Ahmed, M. (2015). The correlation between risk management and organizational performance: an empirical investigation using panel data. *Res J. of Finance and Accounting*, 6(16), 136-146.
- Yahaya, O. A., Mohammed, I., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Board governance and sustainability disclosure of Nigeria Listed Deposit Money Banks. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(5), 126-146.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., & Usman, S. O. (2015). Determinants of productivity of listed deposit money banks: An empirical estimation using panel data. *Journal of Accounting*, 4(1), 79-93.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., & Usman, S. O. (2015). International financial reporting standards and value relevance of accounting information of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Dev.*, 6(12), 85-93.
- Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., Yusuf, M. J., & Bilyaminu, T. (2019). Financial mix and financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Management*, 2(1), 226-237.
- Yahaya, O. A., Tanko, M., & Muhammad, L. M. (2017). Effects of corporate characteristics

on earnings quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Journal of Management Sciences*, 8(1), 47-64.

Yahaya, O. A., Yusuf, M. J., & Dania, I. S. (2015). International financial reporting standards' adoption and financial statement effects: Evidence from listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Research J. of Finance and Accounting*, 6(12), 107-122.

Yakubu, J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). Do board meetings and remuneration influence environmental disclosure? *Asian Review of Financial Research*, 37(2), 150-191.

Yakubu, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). Auditors' characteristics and variability in integrated reporting gravity. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business*, 8(50), 234-255.

Yusuf, M. J., & Yahaya, O. A. (2023). CEO attributes and financial performance of listed firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, 11(2), 112-124.

Zubairu, R., & Yahaya, O. A. (2024). The influence of audit quality on financial reporting quality, mediated by audit committee effectiveness in Nigerian listed companies. *European Management Review*, 21(1), 1-22.

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